

Survey Report

Erasmus+

ReTrans

**Working with Interpreters in Refugee Transit Zones:
Capacity building and awareness-raising for higher education contexts**

Work Package 1

Final Report

**Leader of WP1: Department of Foreign Languages,
Translation and Interpreting, Ionian University, Greece**

Survey Report

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We would like to extend our thanks to:

- **UNHCR Austria**
- **Ms. Eleftheria Pafadelli, Ms. Marina Malini, Ms. Marina Tatsidi, Ms. Ilektra Karamizari-Tsakoteli, Ms. Irene Pournari, Ms. Zoi Sofologi, Ms. Maria Dimopoulou, Ms. Panagiota Pagoni and Ms. Sofia Zangana**, undergraduate interpreting students at the *Department of Foreign Languages, Translation and Interpreting of Ionian University, Corfu, Greece* for working on the design of the questionnaire and making the presentation (see Annex II) at the ReTrans Project kickoff meeting that was held in Vienna on 19th May, 2022.

Please cite this work as: Kozobolis, S., Ioannidis, A., Pasch, H., Heinisch, B., Nuč-Blažič, A., Orthaber, S., Zwischenberger, M.B., Simoska, S., Panova-Ignjatovik, T., Aleksoska-Ckatroska, M., Pappa, M., Iacono, K., Vlachopoulos, S., Pöllabauer, S. (2022). *Working with Interpreters in Refugee Transit Zones: Capacity building and awareness-raising for higher education contexts* (Survey Report). Available at: <https://www.retrans-interpreting.com/research/>

Survey Report

The project has received funding from the European Union. The present document reflects only the authors' view and not the view of the EU; The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Introduction

The present report presents the outcomes of a transnational empirical survey conducted within the framework of the project “ReTrans – Working with Interpreters in Refugee Transit Zones: Capacity building and awareness-raising for higher education contexts”, which is carried out with the participation of partner universities from Austria, Greece, the Republic of North Macedonia, and Slovenia and is implemented with the support of the European Union's Erasmus+ programme.

The aim of the project is to raise awareness for the issue of interpreting in a humanitarian and transborder migration context among students and teachers of higher education interpreter training facilities and contribute to the diversification of didactic materials by developing a range of educational tools. By giving stakeholders in the field (refugees, lay interpreters with a migration background, institutional representatives) a voice and by including and integrating their individual perspectives, the project seeks, furthermore, to promote access and inclusion and aims to provide a forum for exchange between higher education interpreters facilities and actors in the field.

In order to outline current practices and identify challenges of interpreting in the context of refugee transit zones and reception centres, the first project phase (WP1) foresees a survey among public service institutions as the end users of interpreting services and other involved parties in the project's partner countries. Their responses provide comprehensive and up-to-date information on the needs that interpreters and service users (institutional representatives, refugees) have in such contexts, as well as the kinds of dilemmas they are faced with, including the perspectives of actors in the field, whose voice is often unheard.

More specifically, public service personnel and humanitarian aid workers in the field were asked to fill in a questionnaire on working with interpreters, focusing on their perceptions, experiences and expectations. The questionnaire comprised 33, both closed and open-ended, questions and was designed in the English language by students of the Department of Foreign Languages, Translation and Interpreting of the Ionian University, Corfu. After it had been evaluated by the University of Vienna and tested by all partners, the questionnaire was distributed to the local teams of each project partner, in order to be translated in their national languages. Then, it was distributed by the local teams to the end-users of interpreting services in their countries and was made available for completion online from the 15th September until the 31st November 2022.

After that period, a total of 64 valid questionnaires were collected, allowing for an insight into issues of language combinations, duties and responsibilities of interpreters, best practices, ethical challenges, etc. and serving as a basis for the production of the results to be produced in the subsequent work packages of the *ReTrans* project. The following tables show the frequency of the languages in which the collected questionnaires were completed (Table 1) as well as the counties in which the respondents worked at the time of participating in the survey (Table 2). As can be seen from the tables, apart from the project's partner countries and their national languages, there have been few questionnaires that were completed in English, as well as few respondents coming from other countries, namely Kosovo and Albania.

Language	Frequency	Percent
German	19	29,7
Greek	11	17,2
English	6	9,4
Macedonian	19	29,7
Slovenian	9	14,1
Total	64	100,0

Table 1: Languages of the questionnaires

Country	Frequency	Percent
Austria	20	31
Greece	11	17
North Macedonia	22	35
Slovenia	9	14
Other	2	3
Total	64	100,0

Table 2: Countries of the respondents

The following pages provide a more detailed description of the survey results for each individual partner country of the project, namely Austria, Greece, North Macedonia and Slovenia, as well as some general conclusions at the end. For clarity reasons, all national surveys presented below follow the same structure according to specific thematic areas: First, the sample of the survey is analysed with the aim of describing the general profile of the respondents who took part in it. Then, the current situation in every participating country is presented in two subsections: (a) adequacy of interpreting services and (b) degree of maturity/professionalization of interpreting services. The aim of the first subsection is to give an account of the current language needs, the main interpreting modes used in the relevant settings, and the adequacy in number of available interpreters, while the aim of the second one is to determine if the interpreters provide their services in a professional manner and to what extent the main stakeholders consider interpreting as professional activity. A description of future challenges is provided afterwards with the purpose to detect the respondents' opinions on possible current shortcomings as well as their proposals for future improvements. Finally, the national reports conclude with a short summary of the main findings, conclusions and/or trends arising from the survey for every individual country.

The project "ReTrans – Working with Interpreters in Refugee Transit Zones" is funded by the European Union. Project reference: [2021-2-AT01-KA220-HED-000048753](#)

01 Survey Report: Austria

Survey Report: Austria

Introduction

Sample analysis: The survey was sent to a total of 83 institutions and organizations (public service institutions and ministries, NGOs and volunteer organization, and interpreter associations) at the end of September 2022 and was open until the end of October. Some of these contacts further distributed the questionnaire to other relevant organizations. A reminder was sent in mid-October. However, the response rate was low: The questionnaire was filled in by 20 respondents from Austria.

The majority of the respondents from Austria are female (65%), while 30% are male and one person did not prefer to say. The Austrian respondents work in a variety of different fields: The majority (60%) work in sectors that are not related to health care, justice, education, or civil services, while 15% work in healthcare and civil services (Figure 1), respectively. Here, respondents did not specify with which organization or institution they were affiliated, but from the sample, to which the questionnaire was sent, we may assume that a considerable number of them will work for institutions or organizations which provide support to refugees and migrants. Half of the respondents (50%) have been working with refugees for more than 5 years (Figure 2), indicating that they will have at least some, and in some cases ample experience (Figure 4) in interpreter-mediated encounters. Despite this fact, more than half of the respondents (65%) state that they did not receive any training related to working with refugees (Figure 3). This fact may let us assume that working with interpreters and solving problems in interprofessional cooperation will most probably be solved in an ad-hoc and learning-by-doing approach.

Figure 1: Which public sector do you work for?

Figure 2: How long have you been working with refugees?

Figure 3: Have you received any training related to working with refugees?

Current Situation

Adequacy of interpreting services: The aim of this section is to give an account of the respondents' current language needs, the main interpreting modes used in the relevant settings, and the respondents' view on the availability of interpreters.

Some respondents work with interpreters on a regular basis, some less often: The majority (40%) work with interpreters in 25 out of 100 client encounters, 35% use interpreters in 75 out of 100 encounters, and 15% need the help of interpreters in 50 out of 100 client interactions. 10% of the respondents always call upon interpreters in 100 of 100 cases (Figure 4). These numbers indicate that there is a considerable number of organizations, institutions and individuals who have to rely on interpreters in their work.

Figure 4: How often do you work with an interpreter per 100 cases?

In general, professional interpreters, in the sense of interpreters who have received some kind of formal interpreter training, are only sometimes or rarely used in the respondents' view, while the respondents mostly seem to rely on the support though non-professional interpreters (i.e. friends or family members or compatriots).

The main countries of origins to which the respondents provide services are Afghanistan (15 respondents), Syria (13), Ukraine (12) and other countries (11) that are not African countries, or Pakistan (Figure 5). Given the current migration trends in a national Austrian context, that are also reflected in national asylum application statistics, this is not surprising, as these countries have been the main countries of origin over the last few years. Nonetheless it may be pointed out that such trends are volatile and may change rapidly due to geopolitical developments. Over the last few months, for instance, Austria has seen an increased number of applicants for international protection from India, due to a visa-exemption agreement between Serbia and New Delhi. These developments are not yet reflected in the respondents' answers, maybe also because clients from India may communicate more often in English as a lingua franca.

Figure 5: Which are the main countries of origin of the refugees you provide services to?

If the respondents use interpreting services in their communication with refugees, the most frequently used languages are Arabic (13 respondents), Dari and Farsi (12 each), Russian (11) and Ukrainian (9), while Kurdish (6) and other languages (5) only play a minor role (Figure 6). Some of the respondents also mentioned German, which will most probably be the language they use themselves.

Figure 6: During interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees, what languages are most frequently used?

If no interpreter is available for a specific language for a specific encounter, 35% of the respondents resort to using two interpreters, which suggests that they employ some sort of relay interpreting (Figure 7). It may be assumed, however, that neither the users nor the interpreters themselves will have much in-depth knowledge on how to handle such specific communicative formats. In these cases, the language combinations that were mentioned are, again not surprisingly, Chechen-Russian, Arabic-Farsi, Kurdish-Arabic or Pashto-Dari, presumably in combination with German, which is the official national language that is most commonly used in institutional or counselling encounters. Two respondents stated that they work with several languages and several interpreters at the same time, including Dari, Farsi, Arabic, Russian, Turkish. No specifics were provided, but it may be assumed that these are situations in which information is provided to larger groups of individuals (e.g. group sessions, educational situations, e.g. so-called “orientation classes”), which would require specific techniques and strategies on the part of both the primary communicators and the interpreters.

Figure 7: Have you worked with two interpreters during the same session (in cases when no interpreter for a specific language pair was available)?

The interpreting services are mainly delivered face-to-face (20 responses), by phone call (12 responses) or video call (5) (Figure 8). The survey was conducted after the end of the distancing measures that were in place during the Covid-19 pandemic, which triggered a greater use of remote interpreting; these answers suggest, however, that some forms of remote interpreting are continued to be used.

Figure 8: Interpreting modes

60% of the respondents think that there is a lack in the number of interpreters at their institution and more than half of them (12) think that there is an overall lack in the number of **trained** interpreters at their institution. Interpreters are usually not employed on a permanent basis but work on a freelance basis (only 45% of the respondents state that they rely on permanently employed interpreters) (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Are there interpreters in your service employed on a permanent basis?

Degree of maturity/professionalization of interpreting services: The aim of this section is to determine if, in the respondents’ views, interpreters provide their services in a ‘professional’ manner and to what extent the main stakeholders consider interpreting a professional activity.

More than two thirds of the respondents brief their interpreters, 40% of the respondents brief them before an assignment, and 35% additionally also after the assignment (Figure 10). This suggests that the majority of the respondents are aware of the fact that successful interprofessional communication also requires the establishment of some ground rules of cooperation, the clarification of expectations and information on the context (the “case”, expected content, participants) as such.

Figure 10: Are interpreters generally briefed before / after the assignment?

More than half of the respondents (60%) also give feedback to interpreters after an assignment (Figure 11). This feedback is given orally (9 respondents) after the interpreting assignment. This feedback may include the discussion of linguistic issues, e.g. problematic phrases and formulations

(2 respondents), ‘verbatim’ interpreting (1 respondent) –though it remains unclear, what ‘verbatim’ means in this answer, the role of the interpreter or issues of interpreting technique (1 respondent), issues of collaboration (1 respondent), an overall impression of how well an encounter went (1 respondent), or mutual (emotional) coping with the situation (1 respondent). One respondent also stated that the interpreter might provide additional information on a case if they had already interpreted for the same person before.

Figure 11: Do you provide feedback to interpreters after an interpreted encounter?

The aim of the next question was to find out which principles of professional behaviour, as they are often outlined in codes of professional ethics, are employed by the interpreters with whom the respondents work (Figure 12). Only 3% of the respondents stated that their interpreters apply “none” of the mentioned principles and techniques of interpreting, 23% state that their interpreters are punctual, and 20% hold the view that their interpreters are “impartial”. 17%, respectively, are of the opinion that their interpreters know how to employ note-taking skills, which is often seen as a sign of professionalism, and that their interpreters introduce themselves properly. Direct speech, i.e. communication in the first person, was only answered with “yes” by 15% of the respondents, and dictionaries are used only seldom (5%).

Figure 12: Professional behaviour

The main challenges that the respondents identified in interpreter-mediated encounters are linguistic challenges (30%), communication skills (22%), and what was termed “cultural knowledge” (16%). Aspects that were considered less influential were the interpreters’ gender, ethical challenges and the interpreters’ religion. Of less importance in the respondents’ view is the interpreters’ age (Figure 13).

Figure 13: What are the main challenges in an interpreter-mediated encounter?

The next question tried to ascertain what was expected from an interpreter when working with refugees. Interestingly, interpreter training is not considered very important, compared to excellent knowledge of the foreign and native language (55% each), soft skills (45%), or “cultural” knowledge about the refugee’s country of origin (25%).

Apart from interpreting, interpreters are also sometimes asked to deliver other services (Figure 14), including explaining cultural differences (11 respondents), helping to fill in application forms (9 respondents), accompanying refugees to other appointments (7 respondents) or assisting refugees with making appointments (5 respondents)

Figure 14: Are the interpreters also asked to offer other services?

The respondents also work with individuals with specific needs (Figure 15), including mentally ill patients (16 respondents), survivors of abuse (15), illiterate/semiliterate persons (14), victims/survivors of torture (14), unaccompanied minors (11), persons with cognitive disorders (8) or the deaf/hard-of-hearing (5), indicating that this will most probably bring about specific challenges for interpreters. Here it may be assumed that these may prove difficult to solve for interpreters who have not received any formal training in interpreting and who may not be specifically aware of the communication needs of individuals with such specific needs.

Figure 15: Amongst the refugees, do you also work with special groups?

Less than half of the respondents (45%) state that they provide counselling support to interpreters after traumatic cases (Figure 16). This can take the form of (individual or team) supervision (6 respondents), follow-up conversations (3 respondents), coaching, talking with colleagues or counselling staff as well as providing additional information on specific matters.

Figure 16: Is counseling support offered to interpreters after traumatic cases?

Future Challenges

Measures and proposals for improvements: The aim of this section is to obtain an insight into the stakeholders' (employees of public institutions, NGOs) opinions on possible shortcomings with respect to interpreter-mediated encounters as well as their views on potential improvements.

Areas of improvement identified by the survey participants are education and training for the interpreters (interpreting techniques, information on the specifics of community interpreting, issues related to migration and asylum, and refugees experiences and backgrounds, trauma, empathy, communication management) but also training for individuals using interpreting services (what they should know when collaborating with interpreters), (higher) fees for interpreting services, and the establishment of a pool of professional interpreters.

Conclusion

The Austrian survey respondents work in different fields, and all have experience in working with interpreters, some seem to have ample experience and work with interpreters on a regular basis, often in face-to-face situations, sometimes also in the form of remote interpreting. For specific language combinations relay interpreting is used. Some also brief their interpreters and provide feedback to them, and after cases that may be particularly challenging for interpreters, some provide supervision and counselling to the interpreters. Despite the fact that they work with interpreters on a regular basis, only few have received training in interprofessional cooperation, i.e. on how to collaborate professionally and more efficiently with interpreters. It may be assumed that many of the strategies they employ have been developed individually, through learning by doing, and possibly trial and error, to find out what works best for them in contexts that are generally characterized by

an overall lack of resources and where speakers may also have diverse needs (mentally ill clients, survivors of abuse and torture, illiterate/semiliterate clients, minors etc.), as was also indicated in one of the survey questions. This lack of knowledge on the specifics of working with interpreters was also mentioned as one of the desiderata for improvement.

Many of the Austrian respondents work with interpreters having no formal training in interpreting, which might also be one of the reasons why, in the respondents' view, some interpreters are perceived as lacking in professionalism. Interestingly, although the training of interpreters was not considered as very important among the respondents, several respondents stated that education and training are among the key aspects that should be improved. Among the main challenges that were identified by the respondents are linguistic challenges, and a lack of communication skills, next to coping with the clients' heterogeneous backgrounds ("cultural knowledge"). Apart from interpreting, interpreters are also, not surprisingly, asked to deliver other tasks (providing explanations, assisting with forms and appointments etc.). Another desideratum was the establishment of a pool of interpreters and higher fees for interpreters. Even though the survey did not yield a large number of responses, both on a national scale, and in the other project partners' countries, the results underline what is known through other similar surveys: This is a field that would merit much more attention, and that would benefit from awareness-raising and training, also interprofessional training, both for interpreters themselves and their clients as users of interpreting services.

02 Survey Report: Greece

Survey Report: Greece

Introduction

Sample analysis: The first question concerned the country in which the respondents who took part in the survey work: "Which country do you work in?", offering five options in the answer field (Austria/Northern Macedonia/Slovenia/Greece/other). 17% of the questionnaires, that is 11 questionnaires out of a total of 64, indicate that their country of work was Greece (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Country of work

The second question concerned the experience in working with refugees: “How long have you been working with refugees?”. The majority of the respondents (55 %) stated that they have been working with refugees from 1 to 5 years, while 18% for more than 5 years. It is interesting that 18% of the respondents have worked with refugees for less than a year and 1,9% have worked with refugees for a year (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Working experience with refugees

In order to identify the gender of the respondents, they were called to define their gender by answering the question: “Choose your gender – Choose one of the following answers: Female/Male/Prefer not to say/Other.” 64% of the respondents were female and only 27% male, while there was only a minority of 9% that chose not to answer the specific question (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Gender of the respondents

The question “What is your age?” called the respondents to indicate their age range (Answer options: 18-22/23-29/30-40/41-54/55-65/65+). Almost all age groups were represented, with a majority of 36% coming from the age group 30-40, followed by a percentage of 27% from the age groups of 41-54 years, while the age groups 23-29 and 55-65 share a percentage of 18% each, respectively (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Age of the respondents

Figure 5: Sector

In order to identify the sector of professional activity, the respondents were asked to answer the question: “Which public sector do you work for?”, by choosing one of the following options: Healthcare/ Justice/ Education/Security/ Civil services and administration/ Other. The answers in this question were distributed in several sectors with 27% of the respondents working in the education, another 27% in civil services and administration and finally 46% in other sectors (Figure 5).

Current situation

Adequacy of interpreting services: Once the working experience of the respondents along with their general profile have been presented, we will examine next the current situation concerning the adequacy of interpreting services. The aim is to investigate the current language needs, the main interpreting modes used in the relevant settings and the adequacy in the number of the available interpreters.

To begin with, the first question was “How often do you work with an interpreter (per 100 cases)?” The options were 0%/ ca.25%/ ca. 75%/ ca. 100%. The respondents were allowed to choose only one answer. 37% of the respondents indicated that there has been cooperation with interpreters in all cases they handled. 27% of the respondents indicated that out of 100 cases handled none involved working with interpreters. 18% of the respondents indicated that only 25 out of 100 cases involved work with interpreters and another 18% indicated that 75 out of 100 cases concerned working with interpreters (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Frequency of working with interpreters

As far as their working experience is concerned, the majority (55%) of the respondents stated that they have been working with refugees from one to five years, while 18% have been working for more than five years. Only a small percentage of 9% has been working for up to a year, while 18% has no working experience with refugees. However, an interesting finding resulting from the survey is that most of the respondents have received training in order to work with refugees, but no special training in order to work with interpreters. More specifically, the majority of the respondents (64%) stated that they have been trained in working with refugees training, but when it comes to training related to working with interpreters, the vast majority of them (73%) stated that they have not received any respective training and only 27% had the opportunity to receive such a special training (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Training related to working with interpreters

In order to identify the country of origin of the beneficiaries to whom interpreting services were provided, there was the question “Which are the main countries of origin you provide services to?”, with the option to choose up to three answers: Afghanistan/ African countries/ Pakistan/ Syria/ Ukraine/ Other. The respondents were allowed to choose multiple answers and the percentage accumulation in the distribution exceeds 100%. Given the current situation, the main countries of origin of the beneficiaries are Syria (almost 73%) along with Afghanistan (almost 73%) followed by Pakistan (45,5), African countries in general (36,4%) and other countries 27,3%. Ukraine is also a

country of origin of the beneficiaries accounting for 9% of the answers due to the war that has broken out (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Countries of origin

The following question concerned the languages that were most frequently used during interpreter-mediated encounters with interpreters. The respondents could answer it by indicating all the possible option: Arabic/ Bengali/ Dari/ German/ English/ French/ Italian/ Kurdish/ Punjabi/ Russian/ Spanish/ Ukrainian/ Urdu/ Other. According to the answers there was a mediated encounter in almost all the languages presented in the questionnaire. The only languages that were not represented were German, French, Italian, Spanish and Ukrainian. The respondents had multiple answers at their disposal. That is the reason for a percentage accumulation higher than 100.

Figure 9: Most frequently used languages

The language that is, according to the survey results, the most frequently used is Arabic (72,7%) followed by Farsi (63,6%), Dari (54,4%), Urdu (54,4%), Kurdish (36,4%) and Punjabi (36,4%). English has been also mentioned with a percentage of 45,5%, probably used as lingua franca in order to facilitate interpreting. The other languages represented are Russian (9,1%), Bengali (9,1%) and other (Figure 9). This indication shows that Arabic, Farsi, Dari and Urdu are the main languages that interpreting might be needed extensively in the near future.

There was also a question concerning the issue of relay interpreting: “Have you worked with two interpreters during the same session (in cases when no interpreter for a specific language pair was available.” In the answers, there were the options “yes” and “no” and in case of a positive answer the respondents were called to indicate the language combination. In most of the cases the session was carried out in just one language (73%) and in a percentage of 27% with two interpreters (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Relay interpreting

Briefing is of crucial importance in interpreting assignments and there is need to record the current practice. The respondents were called to answer the question if interpreters are generally briefed by choosing one of the following options: Yes, interpreters are usually briefed before and assignment/ Yes, interpreters are usually debriefed after an assignment/ No. In case of a positive answer followed a question “If so, how?”. In this case, the options were: Access to documentation/ Face to face/ Via e- mail/ Via phone/ Other. It is very important that in 27% of the answers indicated that interpreters were usually briefed before the assignment and at a percentage of 46% that the interpreters were briefed before and after the assignment. However, there is a high percentage of 27% of the answers that indicated that no briefing took place (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Briefing before and after the assignment

The next question was “What would you expect from an interpreter when working with refugees?”. The respondent had to evaluate each one of the following aspects separately: Excellent knowledge of the foreign language/ Excellent knowledge of the native language/ Cultural knowledge of the refugee’s country of origin/ Cultural knowledge of the host country/ Previous experience in working with refugees/ Interpreting training/ Soft skills (e.g., empathy, situation awareness etc.)”, by choosing from a scale 1 - 5 (1. Not so important, 5. Of greatest importance). The vast majority of the respondents considered language challenges to be the most important ones (72,7%) followed by ethical challenges (63,6%). Communication skills and different gender of the interpreter were indicated at a percentage of 45,5% each. It is worth noting that the different religion of the interpreter was presented as a main challenge at a percentage of 27,3%, that is almost in one third of the answers. The age of the interpreter was considered as a challenge at a percentage of 18,2% and other issues at a percentage of 9%. The following figure shows the overall distribution of the above-mentioned factors (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Challenges concerning interpreting

Degree of maturity/professionalization of the interpreting services: This section aims to investigate whether interpreters provide their services in a professional manner and to what extent the main stakeholders consider interpreting as a professional activity. To begin with, an important factor in the evaluation of the interpreting services concerns the way interpreting services are delivered. Therefore, the question concerning the mode of delivery is of primary importance: “Are the interpreting services delivered (choose all that apply): face to face?/ via video call? Via phone call?/ other?”. According to the survey results, the usual form of interpreting services is face to face (9 answers), via phone call (5 answers) and via video call (4 answers). It is obvious that face to face interpreting is the most frequent form, while video call and phone call options are also covering a significant percentage (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Modes of interpreting

Asked about their perceptions of the interpreters' professional behaviour, the respondents indicate that interpreters are punctual at a percentage of 54,5%, they introduce themselves (54,5%), they use direct speech (54,5%) and they remain impartial (54,5%). It is also interesting to find out that at a percentage of 9% the interpreters use online dictionaries, -probably for unknown words or phrases. However, on the opposite side, the percentage of negative answers indicates that almost in half of the cases (45%) the interpreters are neither punctual, nor introduce themselves, nor remain impartial. In addition, they do not take notes at a percentage of 54,5%. The following figure shows the overall distribution of the above-mentioned factors (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Professional behaviour

Concerning the degree of professionalization, there is also a question investigating whether interpreters perform other tasks besides interpreting: "Are the interpreters also asked to offer other services, such as: helping fill in an application form?/ Explaining cultural differences?/ Assisting refugees with making appointments?/ Accompany refugees with making appointments?/ Other?". It seems that interpreting is linked to other forms of communication, since in 72,7% of the cases interpreters help fill in applications and in 63,6% of the cases accompany refugees to other appointments. It seems that cultural differences often have to be explained (45,5%). Thus, the work

of the interpreters is linked to a series of tasks in the overall sphere of communication, having probably the form of cultural mediation.

The following question aims to investigate if the respondents have to deal with the difficulties of working with special groups: “Amongst the refugees, do you work with special groups, such as (choose all that apply): unaccompanied minors? / Victims/ survivors of abuse?/ survivors of torture?/ Mentally ill patients?/ Deaf-hard of hearing?/ Cognitive disorders?/ Illiterate-semiliterate? /Other?”. Interpreting tasks seems to be full of challenges, since in 63,6% of the answers the beneficiaries of interpreting services are illiterate or semiliterate, in 45,5% of the cases there are unaccompanied minors, in 36,4% of the cases they are victims or survivors of torture and in 27% of the cases deaf/hard of hearing. The cases of vulnerable groups in need of interpreting services are considerably high and it is worth mentioning that there is a high percentage of mentally ill patients (18%). It is obvious that the challenge, the special handling and the emotional burden are a quite significant part of interpreting and the task, when vulnerable groups are involved, is quite delicate.

The next question aims to examine if interpreters receive support to handle stress: “Is counseling support offered to interpreters after traumatic cases?”. There is only one option to choose from, either yes or no. It is not reassuring that counselling support is offered only in 18% of the traumatic cases. In the vast majority there is no support at a percentage of 82% (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Provision of counselling support

The following question concerns adequacy in number of interpreters: “Do you think that there is a lack in the number of interpreters at your institution?” Yes/ No. It is clear that in the vast majority of the cases there is a lack of interpreters at a percentage of 91% and just in 9% of the answers there is not such a need (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Lack in the number of interpreters

Figure 17: Employment of interpreters

The last question of this section is: “Are there interpreters in your services employed on a permanent basis?”. In only 27% of the answers it was noted that there was permanent basis employment. In most of the cases (73%), there is just temporary handling of the needs (Figure 17).

The current situation is quite complex, since special training is needed in order to carry out the communication process effectively and efficiently. The fact that interpreting is needed in a variety of languages indicates the complexity of the needs in language combinations. Technology- through video calls and phone calls- appear along with face-to-face interpreting, adding perplexity in the factors influencing the provision of the interpreting service. Counselling is needed and provision of interpreting in vulnerable groups should be provided in a comprehensive way taking into consideration the needs of vulnerable groups and all parts involved.

Future challenges

Measures and proposal for improvements: In order to detect respondents’ opinions on possible current shortcomings as well as proposals, the following question concerns the way interpreting is carried out: “Do you think that there is a lack in the number of trained interpreters at your institution?”

Figure 18: Lack of trained interpreters

It is not surprising that according to the answers given, there is a lack in the number of interpreters, as recorded in 73% of the answers given. In only 27% of the answers is stated that there is no such a lack. These results indicate the challenges for the future (Figure 18).

Conclusion

It is evident that the term interpreter is used for individuals providing interpreting services but also providing help to fill in an application, providing explanations of cultural differences, providing assistance in fixing appointments and accompanying refugees with making appointments. The interpreting services are provided in various sectors, such as education services, in civil services and administration mainly.

The majority of the respondents have worked with refugees for one to 5 years and are 30 -54 years old. More than one third of the respondents work with interpreters all the time (100% of the cases handled). Their extensive experience is very useful since they have an overall approach in issues related to interpreting in humanitarian and transborder migration.

It seems that the vast majority of the refugees or migrants come from Syria and Afghanistan while the languages that are more frequently used are Arabic followed by Farsi, Dari and Urdu. In almost one third of the cases, there is also interpreting through the use of two interpreters, probably due to the lack of interpreters having directly the linguistic combination needed.

Ethical and linguistic challenges are considered extremely important by the respondents while there is no clear image in the degree of professional conduct of the interpreters involved, as only about half of the answers indicate that interpreters are punctual, impartial, use direct speech and introduce themselves.

It seems that special training is needed, since there are beneficiaries who are illiterate, minors, victims of abuse and torture and hard of hearing. It is however comforting to know that there is provision of counselling to the interpreters when needed, even if it is rare.

Communication and interpreting needs are extremely high in several sectors but in the vast majority of the cases there is no employment on a permanent basis. These findings indicate that interpreting services are needed in several sectors and that specific training is also needed in handling communication through interpreting.

In order to carry out interpreting in an effective way, briefing and debriefing are extremely important, in order to approach interpreting in a professional and efficient way. The invasion of technology calls for the establishment of guidelines and training in order to take full advantage of phone and video interpreting options and surpass the difficulties that arise.

An overall approach is needed in order to handle the wide range of language combinations needed and guarantee that in all interpreting sessions there is professional conduct, from all parties involved, that vulnerable groups needs are taken into consideration and that all forms of interpreting are carried out efficiently and effectively.

03 Survey Report: North Macedonia

Survey Report: North Macedonia

Introduction

Sample analysis: The survey questionnaire was sent to 82 contacts in Macedonian institutions and organizations (government ministries and public service institutions, NGOs and humanitarian organizations, and translator/interpreter associations) at the end of September 2022 and was open until the end of October. Twenty-two respondents from North Macedonia filled in the questionnaire. Considering their gender, 64% of the respondents are female, 36% are male (Figure 1). This shows that within the social services sector, working with refugees is still a female dominated area of operation.

Figure 1: Gender

Regarding the age of the respondents, 9% are from 23 to 29 years old, 41% are from 30 to 40 years old, 41% are from 41 to 54 years old, and 9% are from 55 to 65 years old (Figure 2). The disparity of the age groups indicates that the majority of them are between 30 and 54 years old (82 %).

Figure 2: Age

Figure 3: How long have you been working with refugees?

According to the survey replies, 55% have been working with refugees for more than 5 years, 41% of them for 1 to 5 years, and 5% for up to a year (Figure 3). We can see from the results that the Republic of North Macedonia has had a substantial experience in dealing with refugees. We assume that not only the refugee/migrant crisis of 2015 and its aftermath, but also other previous crises, which shaped the Macedonian response towards crises, had greatly affected our country. This indicates that all that happens in the Balkan region has a direct impact on the country.

Figure 4: Have you received any training related to working with refugees?

Concerning the training related to working with refugees, 55 % of the respondents gave an affirmative answer, while 45% a negative one (Figure 4). It seems that a complementary effort should be made in capacity building in order to improve the Macedonian institutions for working with refugees.

Regarding the job categories, from the total of 22 survey respondents, 4 of them are social workers, 3 of them are field officers/ coordinators, 2 of them are project managers (1 is a specialist for fight against human trafficking), 2 are civil servants, 2 of them are professional associates (1 is a coordinator for social and humanitarian activity and integration of persons under international protection), 1 of them is a torture prevention advisor, 1 of them is a secretary of an organization, 1 of them is a state advisor for the development and coordination of the crisis management system, 1 of them is a Secretary General of an NGO, 1 of them is a senior protection assistant (UNHCR), 1 of them is an asylum and mixed migration lawyer, 1 of them is a Regional Remote Interpretation Service Coordinator at MARRI Regional Centre (IOM secondee), 1 of them is an administrative assistant and interpreter, 1 of them is working at the Faculty of Philology “Blaze Koneski”, and 1 of them has not

answered. So, the respondents are professionals from different fields that share their experience with working with refugees/ migrants.

Figure 5: Which public sector do you work for?

As far as the public sector is concerned, 14% of the respondents are working in civil services and administration, and 14% in education, 73% replied “other”, which means that they are working in unspecified sectors (Figure 5). The majority of them gave an unspecified answer, while the rest are working in civil services and administration or in education.

Current Situation

Adequacy of interpreting services: The aim of this section is to give an account of the respondents’ current language needs, the main interpreting modes used in the relevant settings, and the respondents’ view on the availability of interpreters.

Figure 6: How often do you work with an interpreter (per 100 cases)?

From 22 respondents only 2 replied that they need an interpreter in all 100 cases (9.1%), 5 replied that they need an interpreter in 75 cases, 4 replied that they need an interpreter in 50 cases (18.2%),

10 replied that they need an interpreter in 25 cases (45.5%) and 1 replied that they do not need interpreters (Figure 6). To conclude, approximately in more than 50 % of 100 cases an interpreter is needed. 40 % of the respondents – 25 cases frequency, 35 % - 75 cases, 15% - 50 cases, 10% - 100 cases.

Figure 7: Which are the main countries of origin of the refugees you provide services to?

The respondents from the Macedonian institutions/organizations work with refugees who come mostly from Afghanistan (86.4%) and Syria (86.4%). On the third place is Pakistan as a country of origin of refugees (63.6%), followed by the African countries (49%) and Ukraine (36.4%), while 27.3% come from other countries (Figure 7). The country of origin of most of the refugees who enter North Macedonia are from the Middle East (Afghanistan and Syria).

Figure 8: During interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees, what languages are most frequently used?

According to the respondents from the Macedonian institutions/organizations in interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees, the Arabic language is used the most (90.9%), then Farsi (81.8%), Urdu and English (50.0%), Dari (27.3%), Punjabi (22.7%), Russian and Ukrainian (18.2%). The other languages are Spanish (9.1%), German, French, Kurdish, and Bengali (4.5%). According to the survey, Italian is not used in R. N. Macedonia in the interaction with refugees. Pashto, Tamil, Lingala, Turkish and Spanish (sic.) are mentioned under “other” languages (Figure 8).

We can conclude that in interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees in R.N. Macedonia the Middle East languages **Arabic, Farsi, and Urdu** are mostly used, followed by English and Spanish as world languages.

Figure 9: Have you worked with two interpreters during the same session (in cases when no interpreter for a specific language pair was available)?

The Macedonian institutions usually require interpreters who work from a language they do not have in their combination through a bridging language. In most cases, one or even two pivot languages are needed for relay interpreting into Macedonian as the target language. In such circumstances, 27% of the respondents resort to relay interpreting (Figure 9).

In most cases when one language is used as a pivot language, **English** is used most frequently, and then **Arabic** and **Farsi**. Furthermore, Spanish, German, Russian, BCS (Bosnian/Croatian/Serbian), Serbian are used sporadically.

From the total number of 22 respondents, 6 answered affirmatively, with the following answers:

1. **Farsi** and Dari; **Arabic** and Somali, etc. = 1 pivot language
2. Urdu into **English**; English into Macedonian = 1 pivot
3. Tamil - **BCS** (Bosnian/Croatian/Serbian) through **English** = 2 pivot
4. Farsi/**English**; Urdu/**English**; Spanish/**English** = 1pivot
5. Kurdish to **Arabic** to MKD = 1 pivot lang.
6. Farsi – **English**; Farsi – **German**; = 1 pivot
7. Albanian – **German** – Serbian; Russian – German = 2 pivot languages

Figure 10: Interpreting modes

According to the respondents, most of the interpreting services are delivered face to face (19 answers), then via phone call (11 answers), via video call (5 answers) and only one answer “other” and specified that it was delivered via “written translation” (Figure 10). Therefore, the face-to-face interaction is preferred when interpreting services are delivered in R.N. Macedonia.

Regarding the language needs, the 22 respondents have noted the following languages needed for interpretation in order of frequency:

	Yes	Percent (Yes)	Total
Arabic	14	63,6%	22
Farsi	13	59,09%	22
Urdu	8	36,3%	22
Pashto	7	31,8%	22
Spanish	3	13,6%	22
English	3	13,6%	22
Hindi	2	9,09%	22
Punjabi	2	9,09%	22
French	1	4,54%	22
Iranian	1	4,54%	22
Dari	1	4,54%	22
Afghan	1	4,54%	22
Lingala	1	4,54%	22
Tamil	1	4,54%	22
Ukrainian	1	4,54%	22
Albanian	1	4,54%	22
Kurdish	1	4,54%	22

Figure 11: In which language(s) do you currently have the greatest need for interpretation?

To sum up, according to the survey respondents, the languages that Macedonian institutions currently have the greatest need for the interaction with refugees are: Arabic, Farsi, and Urdu as the most important ones (Figure 11).

Figure 12: Are there interpreters in your service employed on a permanent basis?

77% of the respondents answered that the interpreters in their service are not employed on a permanent basis, while 23% replied affirmatively (Figure 12).

Figure 13: Do you think that there is a lack in the number of interpreters at your institution?

64% of the respondents emphasize the need for recruiting more interpreters at their institutions, while 36% consider the number of interpreters sufficient (Figure 13).

Figure 14: Do you think that there is a lack in the number of trained interpreters at your institution?

73% of the respondents emphasize that there is a lack in the number of trained interpreters at their institutions, whereas 27% of them are satisfied with the interpreting skills of the interpreters in their institutions (Figure 14).

Degree of maturity/professionalization of interpreting services: The aim of this section is to determine if the interpreters provide their services in a professional manner and to what extent the main stakeholders consider interpreting as professional activity.

Figure 15: Are interpreters generally briefed before / after the assignment?

The Macedonian institutions and organizations generally brief the interpreters before the assignment (68%), and 27 % of them even before and after the assignment. Only 5% do not brief the interpreters neither before nor after the assignment (Figure 15). The interpreters are briefed mostly face to face (63,6%) and via telephone (45,4%) (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Briefing modes

Figure 17: Do you provide feedback to interpreters after an interpreted encounter?

The respondents are categorically divided on the issue of providing feedback after an interpreted encounter (50% / 50%) (Figure 17). Furthermore, 45,4% of the respondents specified that they use different methods in providing feedback to interpreters, ranging from: “suggestions to use first person perspective when translating”, or “tips for better communication in the future”; or “in terms of the success of the task accomplished and then in terms of the success of the project accomplished”; to “communicating the next final step for the refugees”. Moreover, they provide “evaluation of the engagement, observations, comments and guidance for any possible future engagement”, and “debriefing on the level of professionalism and explanatory notes from the interpreter”. It should be noted that there is an interpreter-scheduling platform (**Regional Remote Interpretation Service**) with a rating feature (at the MARRI Regional Centre). Asylum departments in the Western Balkans use this platform and the users (asylum caseworkers) have an option to rate the performance of the interpreter. The interpreter can see their own rating in their profile on the online web platform.

Figure 18: Professional behaviour

Regarding the professional behaviour of the interpreters, 17 of the respondents answered that the interpreters introduce themselves before the beginning of an encounter (77,3 %), 15 use direct speech (68,2%), 15 of them are punctual at the encounter (68,2 %), 9 answered that they remain impartial during interaction (40,9 %), 5 of them take notes during an encounter (22,7%), 1 of them is doing none of the above mentioned (4,5 %), and no one answered that online dictionaries are used (0 %). It is symptomatic and intriguing that only 40, 9% think that the interpreters remain impartial during interaction (Figure 18).

Figure 19: What are the main challenges in an interpreter-mediated encounter?

For the Macedonian respondents (22), the three greatest challenges are the language challenges (14 answers – 63,6 %), the cultural knowledge (10 answers – 45,5 %) and the ethical challenges (9 answers – 40,9 %). Then, communication skills (6 answers – 27,3 %) and the different gender of the interpreter (6 answers – 27,3 %) are considered as particular concern. Also, 5 respondents answered that the different religion of the interpreter (22,7 %) can be a challenge, as well as the age of the interpreter for 2 respondents (9,1 %) (Figure 19). As far as the answer “other” is concerned (5 respondents), the following 3 comments have been given: “so far everything has been satisfactory”, “lack of training of the interpreters” and one was concerned about “the dress code of the interpreter”.

Regarding their expectations, the respondents from the Macedonian institutions and organizations (22) identified and ranked the following expectations from an interpreter working with refugees:

- **Excellent knowledge of the foreign language** is of the greatest importance for 12 respondents (54,5 %), very important for 8 respondents (36,4 %), important for 1 respondent (4,5 %) and little important for 1 respondent (4,5) (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Knowledge of the foreign language

- **Excellent knowledge of the native language** is of the greatest importance for 13 respondents (59,1 %), very important for 8 respondents (36,4 %), important for 1 respondent (4,5 %) (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Knowledge of the native language

- **Cultural knowledge of the refugee's country of origin** is of the greatest importance for 12 respondents (54,5 %), very important for 5 respondents (22,7 %), important for 4 respondents (18,2 %) and little important for 1 respondent (4,5 %) (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Cultural knowledge of the refugee's country of origin

- **Cultural knowledge of the host country** is of the greatest importance for 9 respondents (40,9 %), very important for 8 respondents (36,4 %), important for 4 respondents (18,2 %) and little important for 1 respondent (4,5 %) (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Cultural knowledge of the host country

- **Previous experience in working with refugees** is of the greatest importance for 6 respondents (27,3 %), very important for 8 respondents (36,4 %), important for 8 respondents (36,4 %) (Figure 24). Those results are quite surprising.

Figure 24: Previous experience in working with refugees

- **Interpreter training** is of the greatest importance for 8 respondents (36,4 %), very important for 9 respondents (40,9 %), important for 4 respondents (18,2 %) and little important for 1 respondent (4,5 %) (Figure 25).

Figure 25: Interpreter training

- **Soft skills (e.g. empathy, situation awareness etc.)** are of the greatest importance for 7 respondents (31,8 %), very important for 10 respondents (45,5 %), important for 5 respondents (22,7 %) (Figure 26).

Figure 26: Soft skills

As far as the expectations from an interpreter working with refugees are concerned, excellent knowledge of the foreign language (54,5%), knowledge of the native language (59,1%), the cultural knowledge of the refugees' country of origin (54,5%) and the cultural knowledge of the host country (40,9%) are considered to be of greatest importance. But, **“very important”** are the interpreting training (40,9%) and the soft skills (45,5%). The previous experience in working with refugees is considered **“very important”** (36,4%) or **“important”** (36,4%).

The next question was “In your opinion, who is usually the person interpreting for your client(s)?” The Macedonian respondents (22), identified and ranked the following persons that are interpreting for their client(s):

- **a compatriot** is the person who is interpreting for the client(s) rarely (7 answers – 31,8 %) or sometimes (7 answers – 31,8 %). Only 18,2 % consider that it is often (4), 9,1 % always (2), and 9,1 % think that it never happens (2) (Figure 27).

Figure 27: Compatriot

- **a friend or family member** is the person who never (8 answers – 36,4 %), rarely (7 answers – 31,8 %), sometimes (5 answers – 22,7 %), often (1 answers – 4,5 %) or always (1 answers – 4,5 %) interprets for the client(s) (Figure 28).

Figure 28: Friend or family member

- **a non-professional interpreter** is the person who never (8 answers – 36,4 %), rarely (4 answers – 18,2 %), sometimes (4 answers – 18,2 %), often (4 answers – 18,2 %) or always (2 answers – 9,1 %) interprets for the client(s) (Figure 29).

Figure 29: Non-professional interpreter

- a **professional interpreter** interprets for their clients: often (9 answers – 40,9 %), always (7 answers – 31,8 %), sometimes (4 answers – 18,2 %) or never (2 answers – 9,1 %) (Figure 30).

Figure 30: Professional interpreter

To sum up, usually a **professional interpreter** (40,9%) is the person interpreting for Macedonian client(s), a **compatriot** is engaged rarely (31,8%) or sometimes (31,8%), however, it is never a **friend** or a **family member** (36,4%) nor a **non-professional interpreter** (36,4%).

Figure 31: Are the interpreters also asked to offer other services, such as:

The Macedonians respondents (22) answered that the interpreters are also asked to deliver other services, such as: explaining cultural differences (16 respondents – 72,7%), helping fill in an application form (13 respondents – 59,1 %), accompanying refugees to other appointments (13 respondents – 59,1 %) and assisting refugees with making appointments (11 respondents – 50 %) (Figure 31). Moreover, 4 respondents answered “other”, and specified that they are “providing information”, or “accompanying them to the doctor, or to an institution, or purchasing hygienic products for women”, otherwise “usually none of the above is required”.

Figure 32: Amongst the refugees, do you also work with special groups, such as:

The Macedonians respondents also work with individuals with special needs, including unaccompanied minors (15 respondents – 68,2 %), illiterate/semiliterate persons (15– 68,2%), victims/survivors of abuse (14– 63,6 %), victims/survivors of torture (9– 40,9 %), mentally ill patients (7– 31,8 %), deaf/hard of hearing (5– 22,7 %) and people with cognitive disorders (5– 22,7 %) (Figure 32). In addition, 2 respondents have answered “other”, and one added: “Currently not, but we had cases in the past”, but the other one gave a negative reply.

Figure 33: Counseling support offered to interpreters after traumatic cases

It is surprising that 73% of the respondents (16) acknowledged that they did not provide counselling support to interpreters after traumatic cases, indicating that only 27,2% of them institutions/organizations in North Macedonia are aware of and worry about the interpreter’s well-being and mental health (Figure 33). They also provided specific answers as to the type of support they offer: three of them noted that within their institution trained psychotherapists offer psychological first aid and psychosocial support “to all involved in our activities” (1). Moreover, one of them emphasized that “following larger activities, dedicated sessions for psychosocial support were/are being held”. It is also noteworthy that the Red Cross, International Agency for Migration - office in Skopje provides counseling support for traumatic cases.

Future Challenges

Measures and proposals for improvements: The aim of this section is to detect public servant’s opinions on possible current shortcomings as well as their proposals for future improvements. The public servants that were surveyed (13/22) had identified the following shortcomings regarding the current situation with interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees in R.N. Macedonia: appropriate training that should be offered to interpreters, especially for rare languages (6/12) with a focus on cultural and religious differences (2). Their observations (2) also included the ethical issues and the principle of impartiality that interpreters should adhere to. Moreover, they emphasized the need for regular communication trainings, greater availability of interpreters, as well as the lack of publicly available information as to contact with special and specialized institutions for the support of interpreters if they are exposed to risky circumstances.

Based on the outcomes and results of the survey, it is evident that it is important to raise the awareness of the necessity and the importance of interpreters in the overall interaction with refugees, thereby raising the social status and importance of the interpreter profession at the national level. The respondents especially focused on:

- raising the awareness of the public servants who need to hire interpreters about the methods and criteria for selecting an interpreter;
- raising the awareness of the interpreters that the person who hires them does so on the basis of previously established criteria and in this sense, information about their previous engagement/s is

important, especially when it comes to interpreter-mediated encounters with asylum seekers or foreigners or a victim of torture or inappropriate treatment;

- raising the awareness of interpreters that they should follow pre-agreed guidelines addressed by the person hiring them.

Additionally, three of the respondents suggested the creation of a database of interpreters, or a platform with guidelines for social and cultural specifics and restrictions as self-preparation of the interpreter before actual engagement; as well as updating the lists of court / sworn interpreters and experts in rarely used languages (for example, Farsi and Urdu).

Most of the respondents emphasized the need of employing interpreters and trained experts, and that the formal education of interpreters should include interdisciplinary content so that they are introduced to the specifics of the circumstances in which they might be engaged.

Conclusion

The variety of professionals working with refugee/migrants relevant Macedonian institutions and organizations shows that our sample of participants is relevant and representative for the survey. With regard to the public sector they work for, we cannot have a clear insight as to the professional and educational profile of the respondents, since the majority of them gave an unspecified answer, while the rest are working in the public service sector or in education. Only half of the respondents claim that they had been trained to work with refugees, which leads to the conclusion that a complementary effort should be made in capacity building in order to improve the Macedonian institutions for working with refugees.

Current language needs: In interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees in North Macedonia, the primary languages of the Middle East, Arabic, Farsi, and Urdu are used the most, followed by English and Spanish as world languages. In most cases, when one language is used as a pivot language, English is used most frequently, and then Arabic and Farsi. Regarding the main interpreting modes used in the relevant settings, the face-to-face interaction is preferred when interpreting services are delivered in R.N. Macedonia.

Concerning the adequacy in number of available interpreters, according to the survey results, the languages that Macedonian institutions currently have the greatest need for the interaction with refugees are Arabic, Farsi, and Urdu, as the most important ones. Furthermore, most of the interpreters in their service are not permanently employed, while a smaller number of interpreters are employed in the relevant Macedonian institutions and organizations.

As to the number of trained interpreters available, most of the respondents emphasize that there is a lack of trained interpreters at their institutions. Therefore, the respondents emphasize the need for recruiting more interpreters at their institutions.

Degree of maturity/professionalization of interpreting services: One of the objectives of this survey was to determine if the interpreters provide their services in a professional manner and to what extent the main stakeholders consider interpreting as professional activity. With regard to the professional manner of interpreters during the encounter, most of the respondents held the opinion that the interpreters follow the rules and procedures, and they are punctual at the encounter. It is

symptomatic, though, that they reflect that the interpreters not always remain impartial during interaction.

Usually a professional interpreter is the person interpreting for Macedonian client(s), a compatriot is engaged rarely, however, it is almost never a friend or a family member nor a non-professional interpreter. In an interpreter-mediated encounter, language proficiency, cultural and ethical challenges are the greatest concern for Macedonian respondents. Then, communication skills and the different gender of the interpreter are considered as particular concern. Other concerns that they singled out were lack of training of the interpreters and the dress code of the interpreter. As far as the expectations from an interpreter working with refugees are concerned, excellent knowledge of the foreign and of the native language, the cultural knowledge of the refugees' country of origin and of the host country are considered to be of greatest importance.

Interpreters are also asked to deliver other services, and from the responses of the public servants, we can conclude that the interpreters' assistance transcends translation services and that they mostly accompany refugees and provide assistance to them in administrative procedures. The Macedonian service providers working with refugees have some experience working with people with disabilities, yet it is necessary to train the interpreters how to interact with these special groups.

The Macedonian institutions and organizations generally brief the interpreters before the assignment and rarely after the assignment. The interpreters are briefed mostly face to face and via telephone. Furthermore, the respondents specified that they use different methods in providing feedback to interpreters, e.g. evaluation of the engagement, observations, comments and guidance for any possible future engagement, as well as debriefing on the level of professionalism. It should be noted that there is an interpreter-scheduling platform (**Regional Remote Interpretation Service**) with a rating feature (at the MARRI Regional Centre), used by asylum departments in the Western Balkans.

Future Challenges: The public servants that were surveyed had identified the following shortcomings regarding the current situation with interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees in R. North Macedonia: appropriate training for interpreters, especially for rare languages, on cultural and religious differences, on ethical issues and the principle of impartiality. Moreover, they emphasized the need for regular communication trainings, greater availability of interpreters, as well as publicly available information on specialized institutions for the support of interpreters if they are exposed to risky circumstances.

Based on the outcomes and results of the survey, it is evident that it is important to raise the awareness of the of the public servants for the need of hiring trained interpreters in the interaction with refugees, for the methods and criteria for selecting interpreters, thereby raising the social status and importance of the interpreter profession at the national level. Additionally, the respondents suggested creating a database of interpreters, or a platform with guidelines for social and cultural specifics for self-study of the interpreter. Most of the respondents emphasized the need of employing interpreters and trained experts, and that the formal education of interpreters should include interdisciplinary content so that they are introduced to the specifics of the circumstances in interacting with refugees.

04 Survey Report: Slovenia

Survey Report: Slovenia

Introduction

Sample analysis: The present study analyses the challenges of communication in the transnational migration context among the parties involved in refugee reception and transit centres in Slovenia. Specifically, the aim of the questionnaire was to gain the clients' (i.e., government and non-government organisations and so forth) perspective on public service interpreting (PSI) practices and training. The study featured 33 questions and yielded 9 responses (in total 64 responses were received from a range of organisations). The findings will help the project team to develop training methods and design training materials for lay interpreters and students of interpreting in a sustainable online format and thus help the service to move towards professionalization. In the light of the increase in migratory flows along the so-called Balkan route, PSI is a fast-developing area which will take on an increasingly important role in the spectrum of the language professions in the future.

First, we will describe the general profile of the respondents who took part in the survey. Most respondents (8.89%) said that they have more than five years of experience in working with refugees (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Work experience

As can be seen from the graph below (Figure 2), two thirds of respondents said that they have received prior training related to working with refugees.

Figure 2: Prior training

The majority of respondents (7.78%) are female (see Figure 3) and aged between 30-65 (see Figure 4). Most participants, however, are *aged between 41-54 years (5.56 %)*.

Figure 3: Respondents' Gender

Figure 4: Respondents' Age

Most respondents said that they work in the public sector in general (78%) and two in the area of healthcare and security (11%) respectively (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Area of Work

The Current Situation

Adequacy of interpreting services: The aim of this section is to give an account of the current language needs, the main interpreting modes used in the relevant setting settings, and the adequacy in number of available interpreters.

Figure 6: Frequency of work with interpreters

Based on the number of respondents and their answers, it is, unfortunately, difficult to draw any firm conclusions in terms of how often the respondents work with an interpreter per 100 cases.

Based on the answers to the question on the refugees' main countries of origin, interpreting is most often required for refugees from the Ukraine, followed by Afghanistan, African countries, Pakistan and Syria (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Main countries of origin

The graph in Figure 8 below illustrates what languages are most frequently used during interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees.

Figure 8: Frequently used languages

During interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees the languages that are most frequently used are Arabic, Urdu Farsi, Kurdish and French, Punjabi, followed by Russian and English. Surprisingly, the Ukranian language ranks quite low (cf. Figure 7).

Regarding the question “Have you worked with two interpreters at the same session (in cases when no interpreter for a specific language pair was available)?”, most respondents (7.78%) said that they have previously worked with two interpreters during one session. This is also not surprising given that Slovenian is a language spoken by approximately two million people, which is why it often happens that no interpreter can be found for a specific language combination.

Figure 9: Mode of interpreting

As can be seen in Figure 9, the interpreting services are mainly delivered face-to-face or via telephone. In rare cases, video calls are also used. However, the respondents said that with the exception of sensitive cases, interpreting via video-calls would be less time consuming and would help speed up the entire process.

Degree of maturity/professionalization of interpreting services: To the question “Are interpreters generally briefed prior/ after the assignment?”, 2 respondents (22%) said that they brief the interpreters before the interpreted encounter, 4 respondents (44%) claimed that the briefing takes place before and after the act, whereas 3 respondents (33%) said that they generally do not brief the interpreters (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Briefing of interpreters

With respect to how the briefing takes place, the Slovenian respondents did not give any answers that would further specify the form of the briefings.

With the next question we wanted to know the extent to which the interpreters are given feedback after the event.

Figure 11: Feedback

60% of all respondents said that feedback was provided, and 40% stated that they do not provide any feedback (see Figure 11). When asked to specify, the respondents stated in general that regular monthly meetings are held with the intercultural mediator who works in the local community. Only one respondent gave a more detailed description of the feedback saying that after the interpretation is completed, all interpreters, in accordance with the internal institutional procedures, are provided with feedback. Before the interpretation, they receive an information package, which includes ethical standards. They also sign a data confidentiality statement. It was further clarified that the following activities take place before the meeting:

- the purpose of the meeting is summarized,
- the expectations are outlined regarding the seating arrangements, eye contact, appropriate tone of voice, body posture,
- instructions are given on further clarifications in case questions are not understood, and what is to be done if the interpreters need to take notes during interpretation.

One answer could not be interpreted due to a lack of contextual information.

Figure 12: Professional behaviour

Regarding the professional behaviour of the interpreters (see Figure 12), 6 (66.7%) respondents answered that the interpreters are usually punctual, 7 (77.8%) respondents said that they introduce themselves to the parties involved, 4 (44.4%) respondents said that they use direct speech, 5 (55.6%) respondents stated that they remain impartial, 3 (33.3%) respondents answered that they take notes, 1 (11.1%) respondent said that the interpreters use (online) dictionaries, whereas 1 (11.1%) said that

they do not do any of the above. Although the introduction to the parties involved (77.8%) and punctuality (66.7%) are rated as important aspects of professionalism, the degree of maturity seems to be problematic since the use of direct speech (44.4%), impartiality (55.6%), note taking (33.3%), usage of (online) dictionaries (11.1%) ranked lower.

Next, the respondents were asked to indicate the main challenges in an interpreter-mediated encounter by checking the responses that best reflected their experiences. All respondents said that language challenges were predominant. 5 respondents or 55.6% stated that communication skills represent a challenge, whereas 4 respondents or 44.4% said that they face ethical challenges. The same percentage stated that this was the interpreter’s gender. Lastly, for 2 respondents or 22.2%, the main challenges were inadequate cultural knowledge, the interpreter’s age, and different religion, respectively. In one case the respondent chose “other” adding that the main challenge is a shortage of interpreters.

Given that language and communication skills represent the biggest challenge in an interpreted encounter, we can refer to the fact regarding the question “who is usually the person interpreting to your client(s)? Please rank the following options by frequency?” that only 33.3% of the clients hire professional interpreters and that many still work with friends or family members and nonprofessional interpreters (each 22.2%), and with compatriots (11.1%). Ethical challenges may result from inadequate or non-existent training. This, however, not only pertains to the interpreters but also to clients.

The responses to the question the expectations from the interpreters, where respondents were asked to rank several options by frequency, indicate that 66.7% (6 out of 9) respondents think that excellent knowledge of the native language and soft skills (e.g. empathy, situation awareness etc.) is of greatest importance, followed by the excellent knowledge of the foreign language and interpreter training both 44% (4 out of 9), the categories cultural knowledge of the refugee's country of origin and cultural knowledge of the host country were important to 22% of respondents (2 out of 9), and lastly, previous experience in working with refugees was regarded of great importance only to 11% (1 out of 9) (See Tables 1 – 7 below).

Table 1: Excellent knowledge of the foreign language

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	important	1	11,1	11,1	11,1
	very important	4	44,4	44,4	55,6
	of the greatest importance	4	44,4	44,4	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

Table 2: Excellent knowledge of the native language

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	important	1	11,1	11,1	11,1
	very important	2	22,2	22,2	33,3
	of the greatest importance	6	66,7	66,7	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

Table 3: Cultural knowledge of the refugee's country of origin

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	important	2	22,2	22,2	22,2
	very important	5	55,6	55,6	77,8
	of the greatest importance	2	22,2	22,2	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

Table 4: Cultural knowledge of the host country

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	little important	1	11,1	11,1	11,1
	important	1	11,1	11,1	22,2
	very important	5	55,6	55,6	77,8
	of the greatest importance	2	22,2	22,2	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

Table 5: Previous experience in working with refugees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not so important	1	11,1	11,1	11,1
	little important	2	22,2	22,2	33,3
	important	3	33,3	33,3	66,7
	very important	2	22,2	22,2	88,9
	of the greatest importance	1	11,1	11,1	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

Table 6: Interpreter training

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not so important	1	11,1	11,1	11,1
	important	1	11,1	11,1	22,2
	very important	3	33,3	33,3	55,6
	of the greatest importance	4	44,4	44,4	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

Table 7: Soft skills (e.g., empathy, situation awareness etc.)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	important	1	11,1	11,1	11,1
	very important	2	22,2	22,2	33,3
	of the greatest importance	6	66,7	66,7	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

The fact that soft skills like empathy and situation awareness are of the greatest importance to the users of interpreting services shows that there is an awareness of how interpersonally sensitive an interpreted encounter with migrants can be. Also, the need for an adequate interpreter training seems to be recognized among the respondents which indicates that they would be inclined to hire a trained interpreter vs. an untrained or lay interpreter.

Regarding the question who delivers interpreting services, where the respondents were also asked to rank the options by frequency, the findings were as follows: 33% of respondents are believed to always be professional interpreters, 22.9% believe that the interpreter is a friend or family member or a nonprofessional interpreter, and 11.1 % believe these are compatriots (See Tables 8 – 11 below).

Table 8: Compatriot

A compatriot		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Always	1	11,1	11,1	11,1
	Often	3	33,3	33,3	44,4
	Sometimes	2	22,2	22,2	66,7
	Rarely	1	11,1	11,1	77,8
	Never	2	22,2	22,2	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

Table 9: Friend or family member

A friend or family member					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	2	22,2	22,2	22,2
	Often	2	22,2	22,2	44,4
	Sometimes	1	11,1	11,1	55,6
	Rarely	3	33,3	33,3	88,9
	Never	1	11,1	11,1	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

Table 10: Non-professional interpreter

A non-professional interpreter					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Always	2	22,2	22,2	22,2
	Often	3	33,3	33,3	55,6
	Sometimes	3	33,3	33,3	88,9
	Rarely	1	11,1	11,1	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

Table 11: Professional interpreter

A professional interpreter					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	3	33,3	33,3	33,3
	Often	1	11,1	11,1	44,4
	Sometimes	3	33,3	33,3	77,8
	Rarely	2	22,2	22,2	100,0
	Total	9	100,0	100,0	

In terms of professionalism (what kind of behaviours are considered to be professional), we see that punctuality and self-presentation were ranked highest. Using direct speech was ranked third, and note-taking only fifth, which both undoubtedly indicate that the interpreter is suitably qualified. These answers cannot be linked to Q18, where 33% of the hired interpreters are always professional interpreters, and 22.9% are friends or family members or nonprofessional interpreters. The deviation in the percentage of professional interpreters compared to using friends, family members or nonprofessional interpreters does not explain the fact that the interpreters do not use a note-taking technique or direct speech during the interpreted encounter. In this regard, it would be interesting to find out whether professional interpreters attended e.g., note-taking technique courses during their training.

The results to the question on the different tasks of interpreters (Figure 13) showed that interpreters are still asked to provide assistance with, for example, explaining cultural differences (88.9%), helping refugees with making appointments (66.7%), accompanying refugees to other appointments (66.7%) or filling out application forms (55.6%).

Figure 13: Tasks of interpreters

The above-mentioned answers corroborate with the question on feedback, where during a briefing the interpreters get instructions in case questions are not understood by the migrant. Problematic questions can often be linked to cultural differences which need to be explained by the interpreter. As a result, the high percentage in terms of the need for explaining cultural differences (88.9%) is not surprising.

When asked whether there are special groups amongst the refugees, 77.8% said that they work with accompanied minors and illiterate/semiliterate refugees. Mentally ill patients represent 66.7%, followed by victims/survivors of abuse and victims/survivors of torture in 55.6%. The next group of refugees comprises persons with cognitive disorders (44.4%), deaf/hard of hearing (22.2%). Finally, one respondent or 11.1% chose “other” (see Table 12).

Table 12: Group of refugees

	Yes	Percent (Yes)	N/S	Percent (N/S)	Total
unaccompanied minors	7	77,8	2	22,2	9
victims/survivors of abuse	5	55,6	4	44,4	9
victims/survivors of torture	5	55,6	4	44,4	9
mentally ill patients	6	66,7	3	33,3	9
deaf/hard of hearing	2	22,2	7	77,8	9
cognitive disorders	4	44,4	5	55,6	9
illiterate/semiliterate	7	77,8	2	22,2	9
Other	1	11,1	8	22,9	9

Regarding the question if counselling support is offered to the interpreter, the answers were as follows: 56% of the respondents said that counselling support after traumatic cases is offered and 44% said that counselling was not available (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Counselling support

When asked to specify, one respondent stated that regular monthly meetings are held with an intercultural mediator working for the local community where the interviews take place. Another respondent said that all employees of the organisation he or she works for have received training on (a) how to work with interpreters, (b) psychosocial support training, (c) psychological debriefing. A third respondent explained that medical assistance, psychological support, and access to relevant NGOs are offered. Lastly, one respondent answered only that counselling in the form of conversations are offered.

Future challenges

Measures and proposals for improvements: In terms of measures and proposals for improvements, the aim was to detect public servant’s opinions on possible current shortcomings as well as their proposals for the future. The answers of the respondents included:

- A larger pool of interpreters.
- Mandatory training for interpreters on a regular basis, for all languages, higher standards, and requirements in public tenders (2 responses).
- No specific measures are needed. The main problem remains the lack of interpreters.
- A systemic approach is needed that will tackle the employment status, education, and support for intercultural mediators and interpreters (2 responses).
- Greater operational capacities along with an online access to interpreting services (qualified interpreters to cover the needs of multiple countries). Finding technical solutions when there is a shortage of interpreters such as a fast online access to interpreting services (face-to-face services are not always needed, e.g., crime victims). Uniform interpreter PSI training

(including the provision of socio-cultural knowledge, empathy in public service interpreting, and taking the needs of services dealing with refugees into account).

- Not my area of expertise.

Conclusion

Public interpreting services in Slovenia remain and will continue to remain vital. The challenges identified are mainly linked to quality (e.g., professional standards are believed to be set too low, interpreter training is believed to be inadequate and/or inconsistent, inadequate socio-cultural knowledge, issues with empathy), supply and demand (e.g., lack of interpreters in general, not just for specific language combinations), and work-specific issues (e.g., employment status, support, accounting for the clients' needs). Social challenges identified included gender preference. The findings have also shown that there seems to be an awareness of the importance of briefing, as it mostly takes place in person (face-to-face) before and after the interpreting act.

General Conclusions

The present report contains the main results of four national surveys that were conducted in the respective partner countries of the ReTrans project, namely Austria, Greece, the Republic of North Macedonia and Slovenia, with the purpose to identify challenges of interpreting in the context of refugee transit zones and reception centres and outline current practices. The 64 valid responses that were collected within this framework give an account of the needs that interpreters and service users (institutional representatives, refugees) have in such contexts, reveal the perceptions, experiences and expectations of the main actors in the field when working with interpreters and outline important issues, such as language combinations, duties and responsibilities of interpreters, best practices, ethical challenges, etc.

As far as the profile of the respondents is concerned, the survey showed that they work in several sectors of the public domain, such as healthcare and civil services, and that all have experience in working with interpreters – most of them for more than five years. Some seem to work with interpreters on a regular basis in their normal work routine, often in face-to-face encounters, sometimes also in the form of remote interpreting. However, despite the fact that the majority of the respondents have been trained in working with refugees (sometimes with challenging special groups, such as minors, survivors of abuse and torture, illiterate/semiliterate clients, etc.), only few have received a respective training in interprofessional cooperation with interpreters, i.e. on how to interact efficiently and professionally with them.

With regard to the current language needs, the results of the survey indicate that the languages most frequently used in the humanitarian and transborder migration context of the participating countries are Arabic, Farsi, Dari, Urdu followed by Ukrainian, English (evidently as a lingua franca), Russian, Kurdish and Punjabi. However, most of the respondents admitted that their institutions often face a significant shortage in the number not just of trained interpreters, but of interpreters in general for these languages, and that in most cases interpreters are not employed on a permanent basis. It is therefore not surprising that they stated that family members or other random, unqualified persons take often on the role of interpreters. This lack of a minimum professional framework for delivering interpreting services could also possibly explain the fact that interpreters are asked, according to the survey results, to deliver other tasks besides interpreting, such providing explanations, assisting with form-filling, accompanying to other appointments etc.

In this light, the survey results provide some valuable insights into the critical issue of the professionalisation degree of the interpreting services supplied in the relevant contexts of the project's countries. When it comes to the question as to whether the interpreters provide their services in a professional manner, most of the behaviours that can be seen as a sign of professionalism, such as using direct speech, taking notes, remaining impartial or using dictionaries, are evaluated relatively low (around 50% or lower) by the respondents of the survey. Therefore, the interpreters' professionalism seems to be confirmed only in part. In the same vein, the survey raises some serious concerns regarding the linguistic competence of the interpreters. More specifically, language difficulties rank first among the main challenges that may arise during an interpreter-mediated encounter, while when asked about their expectations from the interpreters, the respondents prioritized the excellent knowledge of the foreign, as well as of the native language compared to other parameters, such as the knowledge of the refugees' cultural background or as

soft skills. Interestingly, pursuing a training program in interpreting – which could be seen as a first important step towards the professionalization of interpreting – was not considered to be very important by the respondents.

However, on the other hand, most of the respondents seem to acknowledge the importance of briefing the interpreters about the details of the “case” before the assignment, and, sometimes, additionally also after it. In addition, it is positive that the majority of the respondents, even though a narrow one, provides feedback to the interpreters after the encounter, while some of them offer supervision and counselling support after a traumatic case. It is also encouraging that some respondents mentioned the lack of trained interpreters, the lack of knowledge on the specifics of working with interpreters and the need for better cooperation with them as key aspects that should be improved in the context of the interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees. These results suggest that at least some respondents are aware of the fact that successful communication in such settings requires interprofessional cooperation and the establishment of minimum professional standards. To conclude, as also stated above in the Austrian national report, even though the survey did not yield a large number of responses in any of the project’s partner countries, the results underline what is known through other similar surveys: This is a field that would merit much more attention, and that would benefit from awareness-raising and training, also interprofessional training, both for interpreters themselves and their clients as users of interpreting services.

The project “ReTrans – Working with Interpreters in Refugee Transit Zones” is funded by the European Union. Project referenc

Annexes

Annex I: Questionnaires

English version

ReTrans Project - Working with Interpreters in Refugee Transit Zones

This questionnaire is part of the **ReTrans Project** - "Working with Interpreters in Refugee Transit Zones: Capacity building and awareness-raising for higher education contexts", which is being carried out with the support of the European Union's Erasmus+ programme.

The aim of this project is to raise awareness for the issue of interpreting in a humanitarian and transborder migration context among students and teachers of higher education interpreter training facilities and contribute to the diversification of didactic materials by developing a range of educational tools. By giving stakeholders in the field (refugees, lay interpreters with a migration background, institutional representatives) a voice and by including and integrating their individual perspectives, the project seeks to promote access and inclusion and aims to provide a forum for exchange between higher education interpreter facilities and actors in the field.

We invite everybody involved in interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees to share their expertise.

The results of this questionnaire will be used only for research purposes and the responses will be treated anonymously. **If you click on "next" you automatically consent to your data being used for this survey.**

Filling in this questionnaire should not take you more than **10 minutes**.

There are 33 questions in this survey.

Which country do you work in? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Austria
- North Macedonia
- Slovenia
- Greece
- Other

How long have you been working with refugees? *

Please write your answer here:

Have you received any specific training related to working with refugees? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If so, please indicate what kind of training:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '3 [Q2]' (Have you received any specific training related to working with refugees?)

Please write your answer here:

Have you received any training related to working with interpreters? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If so, please indicate what kind of training:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '5 [Q3]' (Have you received any training related to working with interpreters?)

Please write your answer here:

How often do you work with an interpreter (per 100 cases)? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0%
- ca. 25%
- ca. 50%
- ca. 75%
- ca. 100%

Which are the main countries of origin of the refugees you provide services to? (Choose up to three) *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Afghanistan
- African countries
- Pakistan
- Syria
- Ukraine
- Other:

During interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees, what languages are most frequently used? *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Arabic
- Bengali
- Dari
- German
- English
- Farsi
- French
- Italian
- Kurdish

- Punjabi
- Russian
- Spanish
- Ukranian
- Urdu
- Other:

Have you worked with two interpreters during the same session (in cases when no interpreter for a specific language pair was available)? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If so, please indicate for which language pair:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '10 [Q8]' (Have you worked with two interpreters during the same session (in cases when no interpreter for a specific language pair was available)?)

Please write your answer here:

Are interpreters generally briefed before / after the assignment? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, interpreters are usually briefed before an assignment.
- Yes, interpreters are usually debriefed after an assignment.
- Yes, interpreters are usually briefed before and after an assignment.
- No.

If so, how?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes, interpreters are usually briefed before an assignment.' or 'Yes, interpreters are usually debriefed after an assignment.' or 'Yes, interpreters are usually briefed before and after an assignment.' at question '12 [Q10]' (Are interpreters generally briefed before / after the assignment?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Access to documentation
- Face to face
- Via e-mail
- Via phone call
- Other:

Do you provide feedback to interpreters after an interpreted encounter? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If so, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '14 [Q12]' (Do you provide feedback to interpreters after an interpreted encounter?)

Please write your answer here:

Are the interpreting services delivered: *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- face to face?
- via video call?
- via phone call?
- Other:

During an encounter, do the interpreters: *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- take notes
- use (online) dictionaries
- use direct speech
- introduce themselves
- use to be punctual
- remain impartial
- none of the above

What are the main challenges in an interpreter-mediated encounter?

Check all that apply.*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- language challenges (e.g. comprehension of the foreign language, use of the institution's language etc.)
- cultural knowledge (e.g. poor understanding of cultural differences)
- communication skills
- ethical challenges (e.g. lack of neutrality, insufficient cooperation etc.)
- different gender of the interpreter
- different religion of the interpreter
- age of the interpreter
- Other:

What would you expect from an interpreter when working with refugees?

(1: not so important, 5: of greatest importance) *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

1 2 3 4 5

- Excellent knowledge of the foreign language
- Excellent knowledge of the native language
- Cultural knowledge of the refugee's country of origin
- Cultural knowledge of the host country
- Previous experience in working with refugees
- Interpreter training
- Soft skills (e.g. empathy, situation awareness etc.)

In your opinion, who is usually the person interpreting for your client(s)? Please rank the following options by frequency. *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

a compatriot a friend or family member a non-professional interpreter a professional interpreter

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

Are the interpreters also asked to offer other services, such as: *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- helping fill in an application form?
- explaining cultural differences?
- assisting refugees with making appointments?
- accompany refugees to other appointments?
- Other:

Amongst the refugees, do you also work with special groups, such as: *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- unaccompanied minors?
- victims/survivors of abuse?
- victims/survivors of torture?
- mentally ill patients?
- deaf/hard of hearing?
- cognitive disorders?
- illiterate/semiliterate?
- Other:

Is counseling support offered to interpreters after traumatic cases? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If so, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [Q21]' (Is counseling support offered to interpreters after traumatic cases?)

Please write your answer here:

In which language(s) do you currently have the greatest need for interpretation?

Mention them in order of importance. *

Please write your answer here:

Do you think that there is a lack in the number of interpreters at your institution? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Are there interpreters in your service employed on a permanent basis? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Do you think that there is a lack in the number of trained interpreters at your institution? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

What measures do you think should be taken in order to improve interpreter-mediated encounters with refugees? *

Please write your answer here:

Choose your gender. *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say
- Other

What is your age? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 18-22
- 23-29
- 30-40
- 41-54
- 55-65
- 65+

What is your job title? *

Please write your answer here:

Which public sector do you work for? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Healthcare
- Justice
- Education
- Security
- Civil services and administration
- Other

The ReTrans Project Team would like to thank you for your time and important contribution!

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.

German version

ReTrans Projekt - Zusammenarbeit mit DolmetscherInnen in Flüchtlingstransitzonen

Dieser Fragebogen wurde im Rahmen des Projekts **ReTrans** entwickelt („Working with Interpreters in Refugee Transit Zones: Capacity building and awareness-raising for higher education contexts“), das mit Unterstützung des Erasmus+ Programms der Europäischen Union durchgeführt wird.

Ziel dieses Projekts ist es, Studierende und Lehrende von Ausbildungseinrichtungen für Übersetzen und Dolmetschen an Hochschulen für das Thema Dolmetschen in einem humanitären und grenzüberschreitenden Migrationskontext zu sensibilisieren und durch die Entwicklung spezifischer Lehrmittel zur Diversifizierung des didaktischen Materials beizutragen. Das Projekt versucht AkteurInnen in diesem Bereich (Geflüchteten, LaiendolmetscherInnen mit Migrationshintergrund, VertreterInnen von Institutionen) eine Stimme zu geben und ihre individuellen Perspektiven einzubeziehen, um so Zugang und Inklusion zu fördern. Über das Projekt soll auch ein Forum für den Austausch zwischen Ausbildungseinrichtungen und den AkteurInnen in diesem Bereich geschaffen werden.

Wir laden alle ein, die an dolmetschervermittelten Gesprächen mit Geflüchteten beteiligt sind, ihr Fachwissen und ihre Erfahrungen einzubringen.

Die Ergebnisse dieses Fragebogens werden nur zu Forschungszwecken verwendet und die Antworten werden anonym behandelt. **Wenn Sie auf "Weiter" klicken, stimmen Sie automatisch der Verarbeitung Ihrer Daten für diese Umfrage zu.**

Das Ausfüllen dieses Fragebogens dauert ca. **10 Minuten**.

In dieser Umfrage sind 33 Fragen enthalten.

In welchem Land arbeiten Sie? *

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Österreich
- Nordmazedonien
- Slovenien
- Griechenland
- Sonstiges

Wie lange arbeiten Sie schon mit Geflüchteten? *

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Haben Sie eine spezielle Ausbildung für die Arbeit mit Geflüchteten? *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Ja
- Nein

Wenn ja, geben Sie bitte an, um welche Art von Ausbildung/Schulung es sich handelt:

Beantworten Sie diese Frage nur, wenn folgende Bedingungen erfüllt sind:

Antwort war 'Ja' bei Frage '3 [Q2]' (Haben Sie eine spezielle Ausbildung für die Arbeit mit Geflüchteten?)

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Haben Sie eine Ausbildung/Schulung für die Arbeit mit DolmetscherInnen? *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Ja
- Nein

Wenn ja, geben Sie bitte an, um welche Art von Ausbildung/Schulung es sich handelt:

Beantworten Sie diese Frage nur, wenn folgende Bedingungen erfüllt sind:

Antwort war 'Ja' bei Frage '5 [Q3]' (Haben Sie eine Ausbildung/Schulung für die Arbeit mit DolmetscherInnen?)

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Wie oft arbeiten Sie mit DolmetscherInnen zusammen (pro 100 Fälle)? *

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- 0%
- ca. 25%
- ca. 50%
- ca. 75%
- ca. 100%

Aus welchen Herkunftsländern kommen meistens die Geflüchteten, für die Sie Dienstleistungen erbringen? (Wählen Sie bis zu drei)*

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffenden Antworten aus:

Bitte wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus:

- Afghanistan
- Afrikanische Länder
- Pakistan
- Syrien
- Ukraine
- Sonstiges:

Welche Sprachen werden bei dolmetschgestützten Gesprächen mit Geflüchteten am häufigsten verwendet? *

Bitte wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus:

- Arabisch
- Bengalisch
- Dari
- Deutsch
- Englisch
- Farsi
- Französisch
- Italienisch
- Kurdisch
- Punjabi
- Russisch
- Spanisch
- Ukrainisch
- Urdu
- Sonstiges:

Hatten Sie schon einen Einsatz, bei dem Sie in einer konkreten Situation mit zwei DolmetscherInnen zusammengearbeitet haben (wenn beispielsweise kein/e DolmetscherIn für ein bestimmtes Sprachenpaar zur Verfügung stand)? *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Ja
- Nein

Wenn ja, geben Sie bitte an, für welches Sprachenpaar:

Beantworten Sie diese Frage nur, wenn folgende Bedingungen erfüllt sind:

Antwort war 'Ja' bei Frage '10 [Q8]' (Hatten Sie schon einen Einsatz, bei dem Sie in einer konkreten Situation mit zwei DolmetscherInnen zusammengearbeitet haben (wenn beispielsweise kein/e DolmetscherIn für ein bestimmtes Sprachenpaar zur Verfügung stand)?)

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Werden die DolmetscherInnen in der Regel vor / nach einem Einsatz gebrieft? *

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Ja, DolmetscherInnen werden in der Regel vor einem Einsatz gebrieft.
- Ja, DolmetscherInnen werden in der Regel nach einem Einsatz gebrieft.
- Ja, DolmetscherInnen werden in der Regel vor und nach einem Einsatz gebrieft.
- Nein.

Wenn ja, wie?

Beantworten Sie diese Frage nur, wenn folgende Bedingungen erfüllt sind:

Antwort war 'Ja, DolmetscherInnen werden in der Regel vor einem Einsatz gebrieft.' oder 'Ja,

DolmetscherInnen werden in der Regel nach einem Einsatz gebrieft.' oder 'Ja, DolmetscherInnen werden in der Regel vor und nach einem Einsatz gebrieft.' bei Frage '12 [Q10]' (Werden die DolmetscherInnen in der Regel vor / nach einem Einsatz gebrieft?)

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffenden Antworten aus:

Bitte wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus:

- DolmetscherInnen erhalten Zugang zur Dokumentation
- direkt vor Ort (persönlich)
- per E-Mail
- per Telefonanruf
- Sonstiges:

Geben Sie den DolmetscherInnen nach einem verdolmetschten Gespräch Feedback? *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Ja
- Nein

Wenn ja, geben Sie bitte an, wie:

Beantworten Sie diese Frage nur, wenn folgende Bedingungen erfüllt sind:

Antwort war 'Ja' bei Frage '14 [Q12]' (Geben Sie den DolmetscherInnen nach einem verdolmetschten Gespräch Feedback?)

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Wie erfolgen die Dolmetschleistungen? *

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffenden Antworten aus:

Bitte wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus:

- von Angesicht zu Angesicht
- per Videoanruf
- per Telefonanruf
- Sonstiges:

Wie verhalten sich DolmetscherInnen während eines Gesprächs? *

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffenden Antworten aus:

Bitte wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus:

- Machen sie Notizen
- Verwenden sie (Online-) Wörterbücher
- Sprechen sie in der Ich-Form
- Stellen sie sich vor
- Sind sie pünktlich
- Bleiben sie unparteiisch
- Nichts von alledem

Was sind die größten Herausforderungen bei gedolmetschten Gesprächen? Bitte kreuzen Sie alle

zutreffenden Punkte an. *

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffenden Antworten aus:

Bitte wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus:

- Sprachliche Herausforderungen (z.B. Kenntnis der Fremdsprache, Verwendung der Sprache der Institution usw.)
- Kulturelles Wissen (z.B. mangelndes Verständnis für kulturelle Unterschiede)
- Kommunikative Fähigkeiten (z.B. Gesprächsführung, verbale und non-verbale Kommunikation)
- Ethische Probleme (z.B. mangelnde Neutralität, unzureichende Zusammenarbeit usw.)
- Unterschiedliches Geschlecht des/r Dolmetschers/Dolmetscherin
- Unterschiedliche Religion des/r Dolmetschers/Dolmetscherin
- Alter des/r Dolmetschers/Dolmetscherin
- Sonstiges:

Was erwarten Sie von DolmetscherInnen, wenn Sie mit Geflüchteten arbeiten? (1: von wenig Bedeutung, 5: von größter Bedeutung) *

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffende Antwort für jeden Punkt aus:

1 2 3 4 5

- Sehr gute Kenntnisse der Fremdsprache
- Sehr gute Kenntnisse der Muttersprache
- Kulturelle Kenntnisse über das Herkunftsland der Geflüchteten
- Kulturelle Kenntnisse über das Aufnahmeland
- Frühere Erfahrung in der Arbeit mit Geflüchteten
- Dolmetsch-Ausbildung
- Soft Skills (z. B. Einfühlungsvermögen, Situationsbewusstsein usw.)

Wer dolmetscht Ihrer Meinung nach normalerweise für Ihre(n) KlientInnen? Bitte ordnen Sie die folgenden Optionen nach Häufigkeit. *

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffende Antwort für jeden Punkt aus:

Person aus
gleichem
Herkunftsland

FreundIn oder
Familienmitglied

LaiendolmetscherIn

professionelle
DolmetscherIn

- Immer
- Oft
- Manchmal
- Selten
- Nie

Werden die DolmetscherInnen auch gebeten, andere Dienste anzubieten, wie z. B. *

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffenden Antworten aus:

Bitte wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus:

- Hilfe beim Ausfüllen eines Antragsformulars?
- Erklärungen zu kulturellen Unterschieden?
- Unterstützung von Geflüchteten bei der Terminvereinbarung?
- Begleitung von Geflüchteten zu anderen Terminen?
- Sonstiges:

Gibt es unter den Geflüchteten auch Gruppen mit besonderen Bedürfnissen, mit denen Sie arbeiten, wie z. B. *

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffenden Antworten aus:

Bitte wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus:

- Unbegleitete Minderjährige?
- Missbrauchsüberlebende?
- Folterüberlebende?
- Psychisch kranke PatientInnen?
- gehörlose/hörgeschädigte Personen?
- Menschen mit kognitiven Beeinträchtigungen?
- (Semi-)AnalphabetInnen?
- Sonstiges:

Wird DolmetscherInnen nach emotional belastenden Fällen Unterstützung angeboten? *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Ja
- Nein

Wenn ja, geben Sie bitte an wie:

Beantworten Sie diese Frage nur, wenn folgende Bedingungen erfüllt sind:

Antwort war 'Ja' bei Frage '23 [Q21]' (Wird DolmetscherInnen nach emotional belastenden Fällen Unterstützung angeboten?)

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

In welcher/welchen Sprache(n) haben Sie derzeit den größten Bedarf an Dolmetschleistungen? Nennen Sie diese Sprachen in der Reihenfolge ihrer Relevanz. *

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Sind Sie der Meinung, dass es in Ihrer Einrichtung einen Mangel an DolmetscherInnen gibt? *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Ja
- Nein

Gibt es in Ihrer Dienststelle fest angestellte DolmetscherInnen? *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Ja
- Nein

Sind Sie der Meinung, dass es in Ihrer Einrichtung einen Mangel an ausgebildeten DolmetscherInnen gibt? *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Ja
- Nein

Welche Maßnahmen sollten Ihrer Meinung nach ergriffen werden, um die gedolmetschten Gespräche mit Geflüchteten zu verbessern? *

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Wählen Sie Ihr Geschlecht. *

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- weiblich
- männlich
- möchte ich nicht sagen
- Sonstiges

Wie alt sind Sie?*

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- 18-22
- 23-29
- 30-40
- 41-54
- 55-65
- 65+

Wie lautet Ihre Berufsbezeichnung? *

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

In welchem Bereich des öffentlichen Sektors sind Sie tätig?*

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Gesundheitswesen
- Justiz
- Bildung
- Sicherheit
- Öffentliche Dienste und Verwaltung
- Sonstiges

Das ReTrans-Projektteam dankt Ihnen für Ihre Zeit und Ihren wichtigen Beitrag!

Übermittlung Ihres ausgefüllten Fragebogens:

Vielen Dank für die Beantwortung des Fragebogens.

Greek version

ReTrans Project - Συνεργασία με διερμηνείς στις ζώνες διέλευσης προσφύγων: Ανάπτυξη δεξιοτήτων και αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης σε ΑΕΙ

Το παρακάτω ερωτηματολόγιο αποτελεί μέρος του Προγράμματος ReTrans το οποίο αφορά τη συνεργασία με διερμηνείς σε ζώνες διέλευσης προσφύγων με σκοπό την ανάπτυξη ικανοτήτων και την ευαισθητοποίηση των φορέων της τριτοβάθμιας εκπαίδευσης σχετικά με το θέμα και υλοποιείται με την υποστήριξη του Προγράμματος Erasmus+ της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης.

Το πρόγραμμα αποσκοπεί στην εξοικείωση καθηγητών και φοιτητών διερμηνείας της τριτοβάθμιας εκπαίδευσης με το ζήτημα της διερμηνείας στο πλαίσιο της ανθρωπιστικής και διασυνοριακής μετανάστευσης, καθώς και στη διαφοροποίηση του διδακτικού υλικού μέσω της ανάπτυξης ποικίλων εκπαιδευτικών εργαλείων. Το πρόγραμμα προσφέρει τη δυνατότητα σε όλους όσοι εμπλέκονται στο εν λόγω πεδίο (πρόσφυγες, διερμηνείς/ διαμεσολαβητές, εκπροσώπους των κρατικών αρχών) να εκφράσουν την άποψή τους σχετικά με τη διερμηνεία και ενσωματώνει την οπτική τους. Με τον τρόπο αυτό, το πρόγραμμα επιθυμεί να προάγει την προσβασιμότητα και την συμπερίληψη, δημιουργώντας ένα πλαίσιο συζήτησης μεταξύ των ανώτατων εκπαιδευτικών δομών διερμηνείας και των εμπλεκόμενων φορέων.

Ενθαρρύνουμε όσα άτομα έχουν παρευρεθεί σε διερμηνευτική συνάντηση με πρόσφυγες να μοιραστούν την εμπειρία τους.

Τα αποτελέσματα του ερωτηματολογίου θα χρησιμοποιηθούν αποκλειστικά για ερευνητικούς σκοπούς και οι απαντήσεις θα παραμείνουν ανώνυμες. **Πατώντας "Επόμενη" δίνετε αυτομάτως την έγκρισή σας να χρησιμοποιηθούν τα δεδομένα σας για τις ανάγκες της παρούσας έρευνας.**

Ο χρόνος συμπλήρωσης του ερωτηματολογίου υπολογίζεται σε λιγότερα από **10 λεπτά**.

There are 33 questions in this survey.

Σε ποια χώρα εργάζεστε; *

Επιλέξτε μια από τις παρακάτω απαντήσεις

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Αυστρία
- Βόρεια Μακεδονία
- Σλοβενία
- Ελλάδα
- Άλλο

Πόσο καιρό εργάζεστε με πρόσφυγες; *

Παρακαλώ γράψτε την απάντησή σας εδώ:

Έχετε λάβει κάποια ειδική εκπαίδευση για την εργασία με πρόσφυγες; *

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Ναι
- Όχι

Εάν ναι, αναφέρετε το είδος της εν λόγω εκπαίδευσης:

Απαντήστε αυτή την ερώτηση, μόνο αν ισχύουν οι παρακάτω συνθήκες:

Η απάντηση ήταν 'Ναι' στην ερώτηση '3 [Q2]' (Έχετε λάβει κάποια ειδική εκπαίδευση για την εργασία με πρόσφυγες;)

Παρακαλώ γράψτε την απάντησή σας εδώ:

Έχετε λάβει κάποια ειδική εκπαίδευση για τη συνεργασία με διερμηνείς; *

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Ναι
- Όχι

Εάν ναι, αναφέρετε το είδος της εν λόγω εκπαίδευσης:

Απαντήστε αυτή την ερώτηση, μόνο αν ισχύουν οι παρακάτω συνθήκες:

Η απάντηση ήταν 'Ναι' στην ερώτηση '5 [Q3]' (Έχετε λάβει κάποια ειδική εκπαίδευση για τη συνεργασία με διερμηνείς;)

Παρακαλώ γράψτε την απάντησή σας εδώ:

Πόσο συχνά συνεργάζεστε με διερμηνείς (ανά 100 υποθέσεις); *

Επιλέξτε μια από τις παρακάτω απαντήσεις

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- 0%
- Περίπου 25%
- Περίπου 50%
- Περίπου 75%
- Περίπου 100%

Ως επί το πλείστον, από ποιες χώρες προέρχονται οι πρόσφυγες τους οποίους εξυπηρετείτε (επιλέξτε έως τρεις);*

Επιλέξτε ό,τι ισχύει

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν:

- Αφγανιστάν
- Αφρικανικές χώρες
- Πακιστάν
- Συρία
- Ουκρανία
- Άλλο:

Στις συναντήσεις οι οποίες πραγματοποιούνται με τη συμμετοχή διερμηνέα, ποιες γλώσσες χρησιμοποιούνται συχνότερα; *

Επιλέξτε ό,τι ισχύει

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν:

- Αραβικά
- Βεγγαλική (Bengali)
- Ντάρι (Dari)
- Γερμανικά
- Αγγλικά
- Φαρσί (Farsi)
- Γαλλικά
- Ιταλικά
- Κουρδικά
- Πουντζάμπι (Punjabi)
- Ρωσικά
- Ισπανικά

- Ουκρανικά
- Ουρντού (Urdu)
- Άλλο:

Έχετε συνεργαστεί με δύο διερμηνείς στην ίδια συνάντηση (σε περιπτώσεις που κάποιος γλωσσικός συνδυασμός δεν ήταν διαθέσιμος); *

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Ναι
- Όχι

Εάν ναι, αναφέρετε τον γλωσσικό συνδυασμό:

Απαντήστε αυτή την ερώτηση, μόνο αν ισχύουν οι παρακάτω συνθήκες:

Η απάντηση ήταν 'Ναι' στην ερώτηση '10 [Q8]' (Έχετε συνεργαστεί με δύο διερμηνείς στην ίδια συνάντηση (σε περιπτώσεις που κάποιος γλωσσικός συνδυασμός δεν ήταν διαθέσιμος);)

Παρακαλώ γράψτε την απάντησή σας εδώ:

Γενικότερα, παρέχετε στους διερμηνείς σχετικές πληροφορίες πριν/μετά από την ανάθεση μιας διερμηνείας; *

Επιλέξτε μια από τις παρακάτω απαντήσεις

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Ναι, συνήθως παρέχουμε σχετικές πληροφορίες στους διερμηνείς πριν από την ανάθεση μιας διερμηνείας.
- Ναι, συνήθως παρέχουμε σχετικές πληροφορίες στους διερμηνείς μετά από την ανάθεση μιας διερμηνείας.
- Ναι, συνήθως παρέχουμε σχετικές πληροφορίες στους διερμηνείς πριν και μετά από την ανάθεση μιας διερμηνείας.
- Όχι, δεν παρέχουμε σχετικές πληροφορίες στους διερμηνείς.

Εάν ναι, με ποιόν τρόπο παρέχετε τις σχετικές πληροφορίες στους διερμηνείς;

Απαντήστε αυτή την ερώτηση, μόνο αν ισχύουν οι παρακάτω συνθήκες:

Η απάντηση ήταν 'Ναι, συνήθως παρέχουμε σχετικές πληροφορίες στους διερμηνείς πριν από την ανάθεση μιας διερμηνείας.' ή 'Ναι, συνήθως παρέχουμε σχετικές πληροφορίες στους διερμηνείς μετά από την ανάθεση μιας διερμηνείας.' ή 'Ναι, συνήθως παρέχουμε σχετικές πληροφορίες στους διερμηνείς πριν και μετά από την ανάθεση μιας διερμηνείας.' στην ερώτηση '12 [Q10]' (Γενικότερα, παρέχετε στους διερμηνείς σχετικές πληροφορίες πριν/μετά από την ανάθεση μιας διερμηνείας;)

Επιλέξτε ό,τι ισχύει

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν:

- Πρόσβαση σε αρχεία
- Προσωπική συνάντηση
- E-mail
- Τηλεφωνική κλήση
- Άλλο:

Μετά από τη διερμηνεία, κάνετε σχετικά σχόλια (feedback) στους διερμηνείς για την απόδοσή τους; *

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Ναι
- Όχι

Εάν ναι, αναφέρετε λεπτομέρειες:

Απαντήστε αυτή την ερώτηση, μόνο αν ισχύουν οι παρακάτω συνθήκες:

Η απάντηση ήταν 'Ναι' στην ερώτηση '14 [Q12]' (Μετά από τη διερμηνεία, κάνετε σχετικά σχόλια (feedback) στους διερμηνείς για την απόδοσή τους;)

Παρακαλώ γράψτε την απάντησή σας εδώ:

Η διερμηνεία διεξάγεται: *

Επιλέξτε ό,τι ισχύει

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν:

- Διά ζώσης
- Μέσω βιντεοκλήσης
- Μέσω τηλεφωνικής κλήσης
- Άλλο:

Στη συνάντηση οι διερμηνείς: *

Επιλέξτε ό,τι ισχύει

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν:

- Κρατούν σημειώσεις
- Χρησιμοποιούν (ηλεκτρονικά) λεξικά
- Μιλούν σε ευθύ λόγο
- Συστήνονται
- Είναι συνεπείς στην ώρα τους
- Παραμένουν αμερόληπτοι
- Τίποτα από τα παραπάνω

Ποιες είναι οι κυριότερες προκλήσεις που προκύπτουν σε μια συνάντηση με τη συμμετοχή διερμηνέα;

Επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν: *

Επιλέξτε ό,τι ισχύει

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν:

- Γλωσσικές προκλήσεις (π.χ. κατανόηση της ξένης γλώσσας, χρήση γλώσσας του φορέα κλπ.)
- Πολιτισμικές γνώσεις (π.χ. ελλιπής κατανόηση των πολιτισμικών διαφορών κλπ.)
- Επικοινωνιακές δεξιότητες
- Δεοντολογικής φύσεως προκλήσεις (π.χ. έλλειψη ουδετερότητας, ανεπαρκής συνεργασία κλπ.)
- Διερμηνέας διαφορετικού φύλου από τους πρόσφυγες
- Διερμηνέας με διαφορετικό θρήσκευμα από τους πρόσφυγες
- Ηλικία του διερμηνέα
- Άλλο:

Τι θα περιμένατε από έναν διερμηνέα που εργάζεται με πρόσφυγες; (Από το 1 «Όχι και τόσο σημαντικό» μέχρι το 5 «πολύ σημαντικό»)*

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε την κατάλληλη απάντηση για κάθε στοιχείο:

1 2 3 4 5

- Άριστη γνώση της ξένης γλώσσας
- Άριστη γνώση της μητρικής γλώσσας
- Πολιτισμικές γνώσεις της χώρας προέλευσης των προσφύγων
- Πολιτισμικές γνώσεις της χώρας υποδοχής
- Εργασιακή εμπειρία με πρόσφυγες
- Εκπαίδευση στη διερμηνεία
- Κοινωνικές δεξιότητες (π.χ. ενσυναίσθηση, αντίληψη κτλ.)

Κατά τη γνώμη σας, ποιος κάνει συνήθως διερμηνεία για τους πρόσφυγες; Αξιολογήστε τις παρακάτω επιλογές ανάλογα με τη συχνότητα. *

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε την κατάλληλη απάντηση για κάθε στοιχείο:

Κάποιος ομοεθνής	Φιλικό ή οικογενειακό πρόσωπο	Μη-επαγγελματίας διερμηνέας	Επαγγελματίας διερμηνέας
------------------	-------------------------------	-----------------------------	--------------------------

- Πάντα
- Συχνά
- Μερικές φορές
- Σπάνια
- Ποτέ

Ζητείται από τους διερμηνείς στον φορέα σας να παρέχουν και άλλου είδους υπηρεσίες στους πρόσφυγες, όπως: *

Επιλέξτε ό,τι ισχύει

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν:

- Παροχή βοήθειας για τη συμπλήρωση εγγράφων
- Επεξήγηση πολιτισμικών διαφορών
- Παροχή βοήθειας για τον προγραμματισμό συνάντησης
- Συνοδεία των προσφύγων σε διάφορες συναντήσεις
- Άλλο:

Μεταξύ άλλων, εργάζεστε και με ειδικές ομάδες προσφύγων όπως: *

Επιλέξτε ό,τι ισχύει

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν:

- Ασυνόδευτους ανήλικους
- Θύματα κακοποίησης
- Θύματα βασανισμού
- Άτομα με ψυχικές ασθένειες
- Άτομα με προβλήματα ακοής/ακουστική αναπηρία
- Άτομα με γνωστικές/νοητικές διαταραχές
- Αναλφάβητους/Ημι-αναλφάβητους
- Άλλο:

Παρέχεται από τον φορέα σας ψυχολογική υποστήριξη στους διερμηνείς μετά από κάποια τραυματική υπόθεση; *

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Ναι
- Όχι

Εάν ναι, αναφέρετε λεπτομέρειες:

Απαντήστε αυτή την ερώτηση, μόνο αν ισχύουν οι παρακάτω συνθήκες:

Η απάντηση ήταν 'Ναι' στην ερώτηση '23 [Q21]' (Παρέχεται από τον φορέα σας ψυχολογική υποστήριξη στους διερμηνείς μετά από κάποια τραυματική υπόθεση;)

Παρακαλώ γράψτε την απάντησή σας εδώ:

Σε ποια(ες) γλώσσα(ες) παρουσιάζεται τη δεδομένη περίοδο η μεγαλύτερη ανάγκη για διερμηνεία; Αναφέρετέ τις με σειρά σπουδαιότητας. *

Παρακαλώ γράψτε την απάντησή σας εδώ:

Πιστεύετε ότι υπάρχει έλλειψη διερμηνέων στον φορέα σας; *

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Ναι
- Όχι

Οι διερμηνείς οι οποίοι εργάζονται στον φορέα σας απασχολούνται σε μόνιμη βάση; *

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Ναι
- Όχι

Πιστεύετε ότι υπάρχει έλλειψη επαγγελματιών διερμηνέων στον φορέα σας; *

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Ναι
- Όχι

Ποια μέτρα πρέπει να ληφθούν κατά τη γνώμη σας προκειμένου να βελτιωθούν οι συναντήσεις οι οποίες πραγματοποιούνται με τη συμμετοχή διερμηνέα; *

Παρακαλώ γράψτε την απάντησή σας εδώ:

Φύλο: *

Επιλέξτε μια από τις παρακάτω απαντήσεις

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Γυναίκα
- Άνδρας
- Προτιμώ να μην δηλώσω
- Άλλο

Ηλικία: *

Επιλέξτε μια από τις παρακάτω απαντήσεις

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- 18-22
- 23-29
- 30-40
- 41-54
- 55-65
- 65+

Ποια είναι η θέση εργασίας σας; *

Παρακαλώ γράψτε την απάντησή σας εδώ:

Σε ποιον δημόσιο τομέα εργάζεστε;*

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε μόνο ένα από τα παρακάτω:

- Τομέας Υγείας
- Δικαστικός Τομέας
- Εκπαιδευτικός Τομέας
- Τομέας Ασφάλειας
- Υπηρεσίες του πολίτη/Τομέας Διοίκησης
- Άλλο

Η Ομάδα του Προγράμματος ReTrans σας ευχαριστεί για το χρόνο και την πολύτιμη συνεισφορά σας!

Υποβολή της έρευνάς σας

Ευχαριστούμε που συμπληρώσατε αυτή την έρευνα.

Macedonian version

ReTrans Project - Интеракција со толкувачи во транзитни зони за бегалци: градење капацитети и подигнување на свеста во контекст на високото образование

Овој прашалник е дел од меѓународниот проект **РеТранс** – „Интеракција со толкувачи во транзитни зони за бегалци: градење капацитети и подигнување на свеста во контекст на високото образование“, кој се спроведува со поддршка од Европската Унија во рамките на програмата Еразмус+.

Проектот има цел да ја подигне свеста кај студентите и кај наставниците во високообразовните установи за обука на толкувачи за спецификите на толкувањето во контекст на хуманитарната и прекуграничната миграција, како и да придонесе за диверзификација на дидактичките материјали преку развивање разновидни едукативни алатки.

Овозможувајќи им на засегнатите актери на теренот (бегалци, толкувачи лаици со миграциско потекло, претставници на институции) гласно да проговорат и да ги изнесат своите индивидуални перспективи, проектот се стреми да го промовира концептот на интеграција и на инклузија и да обезбеди форум за размена меѓу високообразовните установи за обука на толкувачи и актерите на теренот.

Ги повикуваме сите што се вклучени во интеракциите со бегалци со посредство на толкувач да ја споделат својата експертиза со нас.

Резултатите од овој прашалник ќе бидат искористени само за истражувачки цели и одговорите ќе бидат обработени анонимно. **Ако кликнете на „следно“, автоматски се согласувате Вашите податоци да бидат обработени за потребите на оваа анкета.**

Пополнувањето на прашалникот нема да Ви одземе повеќе од **10 минути**.

Оваа анкета има 33 прашања.

Во која земја работите?*

Одберете еден од следниве одговори

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Австрија
- Северна Македонија
- Словенија
- Грција
- Друго

Колку долго работите со бегалци? *

Тука напишете го вашиот одговор:

Дали сте имале посебна обука за работење со бегалци? *

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Да
- Не

Ако одговоривте потврдно, објаснете за каква обука станува збор.

Одговорете на прашањево само ако се задоволени следниве услови:

Одговорот беше 'Да' at question '3 [Q2]' (Дали сте имале посебна обука за работење со бегалци?)

Тука напишете го вашиот одговор:

Дали сте имале обука за работење со толкувачи? *

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Да
- Не

Ако одговоривте потврдно, објаснете за каква обука станува збор.

Одговорете на прашањево само ако се задоволени следниве услови:

Одговорот беше 'Да' at question '5 [Q3]' (Дали сте имале обука за работење со толкувачи?)

Тука напишете го вашиот одговор:

Колку често работите со толкувач (од 100 случаи)? *

Одберете еден од следниве одговори

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- 0%
- Околу 25%
- Околу 50%
- Околу 75%
- Околу 100%

Кои се главните земји на потекло на бегалците со кои работите? (Изберете најмногу три.) *

Штиклирајте колку што ви треба

Одберете ги **сите** што ви требаат:

- Авганистан
- африкански земји
- Пакистан
- Сирија
- Украина
- Друго:

За време на интеракцијата со бегалци со посредство на толкувач, кои се најкористените јазици? *

Штиклирајте колку што ви треба

Одберете ги **сите** што ви требаат:

- Арапски
- Бенгалски
- Дариски
- Германски
- Англиски
- Фарси
- Француски
- Италијански

- Курдски
- Пенџаби
- Руски
- Шпански
- Украински
- Урду
- Друго:

Дали сте работеле со двајца толкувачи во иста сесија (во случај кога нема достапен толкувач за определена јазична комбинација)? *

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Да
- Не

Ако одговоривте потврдно, Ве молиме наведете ги двата јазика:

Одговорете на прашањево само ако се задоволени следниве услови:

Одговорот беше 'Да' at question '10 [Q8]' (Дали сте работеле со двајца толкувачи во иста сесија (во случај кога нема достапен толкувач за определена јазична комбинација)?)

Тука напишете го вашиот одговор:

Дали толкувачите се соодветно информирани пред/по ангажманот?*

Одберете еден од следниве одговори

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Да, толкувачите се најчесто информирани пред ангажманот.
- Да, толкувачите се најчесто информирани по ангажманот.
- Да, толкувачите се најчесто информирани и пред и по ангажманот.
- Не.

Ако одговоривте потврдно, објаснете за каква обука станува збор.

Одговорете на прашањево само ако се задоволени следниве услови:

Одговорот беше 'Да, толкувачите се најчесто информирани пред ангажманот.' или 'Да, толкувачите се најчесто информирани по ангажманот.' или 'Да, толкувачите се најчесто информирани и пред и по ангажманот.' at question '12 [Q10]' (Дали толкувачите се соодветно информирани пред/по ангажманот?)

Штиклирајте колку што ви треба

Одберете ги **сите** што ви требаат:

- Пристап до документација
- Лице в лице
- Преку е-пошта
- Преку телефон
- Друго:

Дали им давате повратни информации на толкувачите по толкувањето? *

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Да
- Не

Ако одговоривте потврдно, Ве молиме дообјаснете:

Одговорете на прашањево само ако се задоволени следниве услови:

Одговорот беше 'Да' at question '14 [Q12]' (Дали им давате повратни информации на толкувачите по толкувањето?)

Тука напишете го вашиот одговор:

Дали услугите за толкување се испорачуваат: *

Штиклирајте колку што ви треба

Одберете ги **сите** што ви требаат:

- лице в лице?
- преку видеоповик?
- преку телефонски повик?
- Друго:

За време на интеракцијата, дали толкувачите: *

Штиклирајте колку што ви треба

Одберете ги **сите** што ви требаат:

- фаќаат белешки?
- користат (онлајн) речници?
- зборуваат во директен говор?
- се претставуваат?
- пристигнуваат навреме?
- се непристрасни?
- ниту едно од горенаведените

Кои се главните предизвици при работењето со посредство на толкувач? *

Штиклирајте колку што ви треба

Одберете ги **сите** што ви требаат:

- Јазични предизвици (на пр., разбирање на странскиот јазик, употреба на јазикот на институцијата итн.)
- Културолошки познавања (на пр., слабо познавање на културните разлики)
- Комуникациски вештини
- Етички предизвици (на пр., недостиг од неутралност, недоволна соработка итн.)
- Различен пол на толкувачот
- Различна религија на толкувачот
- Возраста на толкувачот
- Друго:

Што би очекувале од толкувачот при интеракцијата со бегалци? (1: не е толку важно; 5: од најголема важност) *

Одберете соодветен одговор за секоја ставка:

1 2 3 4 5

- Одлично познавање на странскиот јазик
- Одлично познавање на мајчиниот јазик
- Познавање на културата на земјата од каде што потекнува бегалецот
- Познавање на културата на земјата домаќин
- Претходно искуство при работа со бегалци
- Обука за толкувачот

- „Меки“ вештини (на пр., емпатија, свест за ситуацијата итн.)

Според Ваше мислење, кое лице вообичаено толкува за Вашите клиенти? Ве молиме рангирајте ги следните опции по фреквенција. *

Одберете соодветен одговор за секоја ставка:

- | | сонародник | пријател или член на семејството | непрофесионален толкувач | професионален толкувач |
|-------------|------------|----------------------------------|--------------------------|------------------------|
| • секогаш | | | | |
| • често | | | | |
| • понекогаш | | | | |
| • ретко | | | | |
| • никогаш | | | | |

Дали се бара од толкувачите да понудат и други услуги, какви што се: *

Штиклирајте колку што ви треба

Одберете ги **сите** што ви требаат:

- помош при пополнување формулар за аплицирање?
- објаснување на културните разлики?
- да им помагаат на бегалците при закажување термини?
- да ги придружуваат на други средби?
- Друго:

Дали работите и со посебни групи бегалци, како на пр.: *

Штиклирајте колку што ви треба

Одберете ги **сите** што ви требаат:

- малолетници без придружба?
- жртви на злоупотреба?
- жртви на тортура?
- ментално болни пациенти?
- глуви/наглуви?
- со когнитивни нарушувања?
- неписмени/полуписмени?
- Друго:

Дали им се нуди советодавна поддршка на толкувачите по трауматски случаи? *

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Да
- Не

Ако одговоривте потврдно, Ве молиме дообјаснете:

Одговорете на прашањево само ако се задоволени следниве услови:

Одговорот беше 'Да' at question '23 [Q21]' (Дали им се нуди советодавна поддршка на толкувачите по трауматски случаи?)

Тука напишете го вашиот одговор:

За кој јазик, односно за кои јазици моментално имате најголема потреба за толкувач? Наведете ги по важност. *

Тука напишете го вашиот одговор:

Дали сметате дека има недостиг од толкувачи во Вашата институција? *

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Да
- Не

Дали во Вашата служба се вработени толкувачи на неопределено работно време? *

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Да
- Не

Дали сметате дека има недостиг од обучени толкувачи во Вашата институција? *

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Да
- Не

Какви мерки, според Вас, треба да се преземат за да се подобри интеракцијата со бегалците со посредство на толкувач? *

Тука напишете го вашиот одговор:

Наведете го Вашиот пол. *

Одберете еден од следниве одговори

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Женски
- Машки
- Не би сакал/а да кажам
- Друго

На која возраст сте? *

Одберете еден од следниве одговори

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- 18–22
- 23–29
- 30–40
- 41–54
- 55–65
- 65+

Кој е називот на Вашето работно место?*

Тука напишете го вашиот одговор:

Во кој јавен сектор работите?*

Одберете **само едно** од следниве:

- Здравство
- Правда
- Образование
- Безбедност
- Државни служби и администрација
- Друго

Тимот на проектот РеТранс Ви се заблагодарува за одвоеното време и за Вашиот значаен придонес!

Поднесете ја анкетата

Ви благодариме што ја пополнивте анкетата.

Slovenian version

ReTrans Project - Delo s tolmači v begunskih tranzitnih območjih: Krepitev zmogljivosti in ozaveščanje za področje visokega šolstva

Vprašalnik je del projekta **ReTrans** - "Delo s tolmači v begunskih tranzitnih območjih: Krepitev zmogljivosti in ozaveščanje za področje visokega šolstva", ki se izvaja ob podpori programa Evropske unije Erasmus+.

Cilj tega projekta je ozaveščati študente in učitelje visokošolskih ustanov za izobraževanje tolmačev o tolmačenju v humanitarnem in čezmejnem migracijskem kontekstu ter prispevati k raznolikosti didaktičnih gradiv z razvojem različnih izobraževalnih orodij. S tem, ko projekt daje glas zainteresiranim stranem na tem področju (beguncem, laičnim tolmačem z migracijskim ozadjem, predstavnikom institucij), ter vključuje in integrira njihove individualne perspektive, si prizadeva spodbujati dostopnost in vključenost ter zagotoviti forum za izmenjavo med visokošolskimi ustanovami za tolmačenje in akterji na tem področju.

Vabimo vse, ki sodelujejo pri tolmačenih dogodkih z begunci, da z nami delijo svoje znanje in izkušnje. Rezultati tega vprašalnika bodo uporabljeni izključno v raziskovalne namene, odgovori pa bodo obravnavani anonimno.

S klikom na "Naprej" boste samodejno izrazili strinjanje z obdelavo vaših podatkov za to raziskavo.

Izpolnjevanje vprašalnika traja približno **10 minut**.

There are 33 questions in this survey.

V kateri državi delate? *

Izberite enega od naslednjih odgovorov

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Avstrija
- Severna Makedonija
- Slovenija
- Grčija
- Drugo

Kako dolgo delate z begunci? *

Vpišite vaš odgovor:

Ali ste se udeležili kakšnega usposabljanja za delo z begunci? *

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Da
- Ne

Če da, prosimo, navedite, za kakšno vrsto usposabljanja je šlo:

Na to vprašanje odgovorite samo, če je zadoščeno naslednjim pogojem:

Odgovor je bil 'Da' pri vprašanju '3 [Q2]' (Ali ste se udeležili kakšnega usposabljanja za delo z begunci?)

Vpišite vaš odgovor:

Ali ste se udeležili kakšnega usposabljanja za delo s tolmači? *

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Da
- Ne

Če da, prosimo, navedite, za kakšno vrsto usposabljanja je šlo:

Na to vprašanje odgovorite samo, če je zadoščeno naslednjim pogojem:

Odgovor je bil 'Da' pri vprašanju '5 [Q3]' (Ali ste se udeležili kakšnega usposabljanja za delo s tolmači?)

Vpišite vaš odgovor:

Kako pogosto delate s tolmači (na 100 primerov)? *

Izberite enega od naslednjih odgovorov

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- 0 %
- pribl. 25 %
- pribl. 50 %
- pribl. 75 %
- pribl. 100 %

Iz katerih držav večinoma prihajajo begunci, za katere izvajate storitve? (Označite največ tri.)*

Označite vse, ki ustrezajo

Prosimo, izberite **vse** odgovore, ki ustrezajo:

- Afganistan
- Afriške države
- Pakistan
- Sirija
- Ukrajina
- Drugo:

Kateri jeziki se najpogosteje uporabljajo pri tolmačenih dogodkih z begunci? *

Označite vse, ki ustrezajo

Prosimo, izberite **vse** odgovore, ki ustrezajo:

- arabščina
- bengalščina
- dari
- nemščina
- angleščina
- farsi
- francoščina
- italijanščina
- kurdščina
- pandžabščina
- ruščina
- španščina
- ukrajinščina
- urdujščina
- Drugo:

Ali ste že kdaj delali z dvema tolmačema na istem dogodku (kadar tolmač za specifično jezikovno kombinacijo ni bil na voljo)?*

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Da
- Ne

Če da, prosimo, navedite, za katero jezikovno kombinacijo?

Na to vprašanje odgovorite samo, če je zadoščeno naslednjim pogojem:

Odgovor je bil 'Da' pri vprašanju '10 [Q8]' (Ali ste že kdaj delali z dvema tolmačema na istem dogodku (kadar tolmač za specifično jezikovno kombinacijo ni bil na voljo)?)

Vpišite vaš odgovor:

Ali se s tolmači načeloma opravi pripravljalni sestanek pred/po tolmaškem nastopu? *

Izberite enega od naslednjih odgovorov

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Da, s tolmači se ponavadi opravi pripravljalni sestanek (briefing) pred tolmaškim nastopom.
- Da, s tolmači se ponavadi opravi zaključna refleksija (debriefing) po tolmaškem nastopu.
- Da, s tolmači se ponavadi opravi pripravljalni sestanek (briefing) pred tolmaškim nastopom in zaključna refleksija (debriefing) po tolmaškem nastopu.
- Ne.

Če da, na kakšen način?

Na to vprašanje odgovorite samo, če je zadoščeno naslednjim pogojem:

Odgovor je bil 'Da, s tolmači se ponavadi opravi pripravljalni sestanek (briefing) pred tolmaškim nastopom.

' ali 'Da, s tolmači se ponavadi opravi zaključna refleksija (debriefing) po tolmaškem nastopu. ' ali 'Da, s tolmači se ponavadi opravi pripravljalni sestanek (briefing) pred tolmaškim nastopom in zaključna refleksija (debriefing) po tolmaškem nastopu. ' pri vprašanju '12 [Q10]' (Ali se s tolmači načeloma opravi pripravljalni sestanek pred/po tolmaškem nastopu?)

Označite vse, ki ustrezajo

Prosimo, izberite **vse** odgovore, ki ustrezajo:

- Dostop do dokumentacije.
- V živo.
- Po elektronski pošti.
- Po telefonu.
- Drugo:

Ali prejmejo tolmači po tolmaškem nastopu od vas povratne informacije? *

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Da
- Ne

Če da, prosimo, podrobneje opišite:

Na to vprašanje odgovorite samo, če je zadoščeno naslednjim pogojem:

Odgovor je bil 'Da' pri vprašanju '14 [Q12]' (Ali prejmejo tolmači po tolmaškem nastopu od vas povratne informacije?)

Vpišite vaš odgovor:

Ali poteka tolmačenje: *

Označite vse, ki ustrezajo

Prosimo, izberite **vse** odgovore, ki ustrezajo:

- v živo?
- prek video povezave?
- prek telefonskega klica?
- Drugo:

Ali tolmači med tolmaškim nastopom: *

Označite vse, ki ustrezajo

Prosimo, izberite **vse** odgovore, ki ustrezajo:

- delajo z zapiski
- uporabljajo (spletne) slovarje
- uporabljajo premi govor
- se predstavijo
- so ponavadi točni
- ostajajo nevtralni
- Nič od zgoraj navedenega.

Kateri so glavni izzivi tolmačenega dogodka? Prosimo, označite vse ustrezne odgovore. *

Označite vse, ki ustrezajo

Prosimo, izberite **vse** odgovore, ki ustrezajo:

- jezikovni izzivi (npr. razumevanje tujega jezika, uporaba institucionalnega jezika itd.)
- znanje o kulturi (npr. slabo razumevanje kulturnih razlik)
- komunikacijske spretnosti
- etični izzivi (npr. premalo nevtralnosti, nezadostno sodelovanje itd.)
- drug spol tolmača
- druga veroizpoved tolmača
- starost tolmača
- Drugo:

Kaj pričakujete od tolmača, ki dela z begunci? (1: ni tako pomembno, 5: zelo je pomembno) *

Prosimo, izberite primeren odziv za vsako trditev:

1 2 3 4 5

- odlično znanje tujega jezika
- odlično znanje maternega jezika
- poznavanje kulture države izvora begunca
- poznavanje kulture države gostiteljice
- predhodne izkušnje z delom z begunci
- usposabljanje s področja tolmačenja
- mehke spretnosti (npr. empatija, situacijsko zavedanje itd.)

Kdo je po vašem mnenju oseba, ki ponavadi tolmači za vaše kliente? Prosimo, razvrstite naslednje možne odgovore po pogostosti? *

Prosimo, izberite primeren odziv za vsako trditev:

- | | rojak | prijatelj ali član družine | neprofesionalni tolmač | profesionalni tolmač |
|-----------|-------|----------------------------|------------------------|----------------------|
| • vedno | | | | |
| • pogosto | | | | |
| • včasih | | | | |
| • redko | | | | |
| • nikoli | | | | |

Ali se od tolmačev zahteva, da opravljajo tudi druge naloge, kot na primer: *

Označite vse, ki ustrezajo

Prosimo, izberite **vse** odgovore, ki ustrezajo:

- pomoč pri izpolnjevanju obrazcev?
- razlaga kulturnih razlik?
- pomoč beguncem pri dogovarjanju za termine?
- spremljanje beguncev na druge termine?
- Drugo:

Ali med begunci delate tudi z drugimi posebnimi skupinami, kot na primer: *

Označite vse, ki ustrezajo

Prosimo, izberite **vse** odgovore, ki ustrezajo:

- mladoletniki brez spremstva?
- žrtvami zlorab?
- žrtvami mučenja?
- duševno bolnimi pacienti?
- gluhih/naglušnih?
- osebami s kognitivnimi motnjami?
- nepismenimi/polpismenimi?
- Drugo:

Ali se tolmačem nudi svetovalna podpora po travmatičnih dogodkih? *

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Da
- Ne

Če da, prosimo, opišite natančneje:

Na to vprašanje odgovorite samo, če je zadoščeno naslednjim pogojem:

Odgovor je bil 'Da' pri vprašanju '23 [Q21]' (Ali se tolmačem nudi svetovalna podpora po travmatičnih dogodkih?)

Vpišite vaš odgovor:

Za kateri jezik/katere jezike imate trenutno največje potrebe po tolmačenju? Navedite jih po pomembnosti. *

Vpišite vaš odgovor:

Ali menite, da je v vaši ustanovi premalo tolmačev? *

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Da
- Ne

Ali so tolmači pri vas zaposleni za nedoločen čas? *

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Da
- Ne

Ali menite, da je v vaši ustanovi premalo usposobljenih tolmačev? *

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- Da
- Ne

Kakšne ukrepe bi morali po vašem mnenju sprejeti, da bi izboljšali tolmačene dogodke z migranti? *

Vpišite vaš odgovor:

Prosimo, izberite svoj spol.*

Izberite enega od naslednjih odgovorov

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- ženski
- moški
- ne želim navesti
- Drugo

Koliko ste stari?*

Izberite enega od naslednjih odgovorov

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- 18-22
- 23-29
- 30-40
- 41-54
- 55-65
- 65+

Kakšen je naziv vašega delovnega mesta?*

Vpišite vaš odgovor:

Na katerem področju javne uprave delate?*

Prosimo, izberite **samo eno** izmed možnosti:

- zdravstvo
- pravosodje
- izobraževanje
- varnost
- javna uprava in administracija
- Drugo

Projektni tim ReTrans se vam zahvaljuje za vaš čas in pomemben prispevek!

Pošlji anketo.

Najlepša hvala za sodelovanje v anketi.

Annex II: Presentation of the questionnaire design process at the Project kickoff meeting (Vienna, 19 May, 2022)